

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

*A non-profit
environmental
research center affiliated
with the
UNIVERSITY OF BERGEN*

*Edv. Griegsvei 3a
N-5059 Bergen, Norway
Tel: 47 55297288
Fax: 47 55200050
<http://www.nrsc.no>*

NERSC TECHNICAL REPORT NO. 206

SEA ICE MONITORING BY SATELLITES IN THE SVALBARD AREA

APPLICATIONS AND TESTS OF ALGORITHMS

A JOINT PROJECT BETWEEN NORWEGIAN POLAR INSTITUTE, NORUT IT AND

NERSC FUNDED BY THE NORWEGIAN SPACE CENTRE

1999 - 2001

Investigators:

Stein Sandven, Kjell Kloster, Torill Hamre and Øyvind Dalen

December 2001

**NANSEN ENVIRONMENTAL AND REMOTE
SENSING CENTER
(NERSC)**

Edv. Griegsvei 3a

N-5059 Bergen, Norway

Phone: +47 55 29 72 88

Fax: +47 55 20 00 50

e-mail: stein.sandven@nrsc.no

<http://www.nrsc.no>

TITLE SEA ICE MONITORING BY SATELLITES IN THE SVALBARD AREA Applications and tests of algorithms	REPORT IDENTIFICATION NERSC Technical report no. 206
CLIENT Norwegian Space Centre and Norwegian Polar Institute	CONTRACT NP-prosjekt 4671
CLIENT REFERENCE Guro Dahle Strøm (NSC) Stein Tronstad (NP)	AVAILABILITY Open
INVESTIGATORS Stein Sandven, Kjell Kloster Torill Hamre and Øyvind Dalen	AUTHORISATION Bergen: December 2001 DIRECTOR Ola M. Johannessen

Contents

1. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES	3
2. REVIEW OF SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING METHODS AND INSTRUMENTS.....	5
2.1 BASIC REMOTE SENSING PARAMETERS	6
2.1.1 Albedo	6
2.1.2 Surface temperature	6
2.1.3 Brightness temperature	6
2.1.4 Radar backscatter coefficient.....	7
2.2 INSTRUMENTS AND SATELLITES.....	7
2.2.1 Radar instruments	7
2.2.2 Passive microwave instruments.	8
2.2.3 Optical instruments.	9
3. DATA AVAILABLE FOR THE PROJECT.....	11
3.1 SATELLITE DATA ACQUIRED IN THE PROJECT PERIOD.....	11
3.2 AERIAL PHOTOGRAPHS FROM STORFJORDEN.....	12
3.3 COMPARISON OF SAR IMAGE WITH AERIAL PHOTOGRAPHS	14
3.4 DATA FROM OTHER EXPERIMENTS AND AREAS.....	15
4. ICE CHARTING SYMBOLS AND NOMENCLATURE	16
5. PROCESSING OF AVHRR DATA.....	19
5.1 RETRIEVAL OF SURFACE ALBEDO AND TEMPERATURE.....	19
5.2 PROCESSING SYSTEM AND EXAMPLES.....	19
5.3 DETAILS OF THE PROCESSING.	21
5.4 EXAMPLES OF TEMPERATURE AND ALBEDO MAPS FROM AVHRR IMAGES	24
5.5 ICE FORMATION RATE, SALT REJECTION AND RELATED PARAMETERS	29
6. USE OF SAR IN SEA ICE CLASSIFICATION	32
6.1 GENERAL INTERACTION BETWEEN SAR AND SEA ICE	32
6.2 SIZEX 92 ANALYSIS OF SAR IMAGES AND IN SITU MEASUREMENTS	33
6.2.1 Zone A: The interior of the ice pack.....	33
6.2.2 Zone B: The small floe area.....	34
6.2.3 Zone C: The area of ice formation.....	35
6.2.4 Comparison of classification by simple thresholding and texture analysis.....	36
6.2.5 Summer conditions.....	37
6.3 CONCLUSION FROM THE SAR ICE CLASSIFICATION STUDY	38
6.4 SAR ICE CLASSIFICATION IN STORFJORDEN	38
6.5 COMPARISON OF SAR AND AVHRR IMAGES.....	42
7. STUDY OF ICE RIDGES AND LEADS IN SATELLITE IMAGES	43
7.1 REVIEW OF A PREVIOUS STUDY ON RIDGES IN BOTHNIAN BAY	43
7.1.2 Use of Fine-resolution RADARSAT images.....	43

7.1.2 <i>Optical images: aircraft photographs and satellite images from Resurs MSU-E</i>	45
7.1.3 <i>Use of laser altimeter measurements of ridges</i>	46
7.1.4 <i>Preliminary conclusions on the Bothnian Bay study</i>	47
7.2 REQUIREMENTS FOR OBSERVATIONS IN STORFJORDEN	47
7.3 LEADS IDENTIFICATION IN SAR IMAGES FROM STORFJORDEN	48
7.4 LEADS AND POLYNYAS IN AVHRR IMAGES	48
8. REVIEW OF THE POSSIBILITIES TO ESTIMATE ICE THICKNESS FROM SATELLITE DATA	50
8.1 ICE THICKNESS FROM AVHRR DATA	50
8.2 ICE THICKNESS RETRIEVAL FROM SAR.....	50
8.3 ICE THICKNESS RETRIEVAL FROM RADAR ALTIMETER	51
9. ICE DRIFT FROM SATELLITE DATA.....	52
9.1 INTRODUCTION	52
9.2 ICE DRIFT FROM SSM/I DATA	52
9.3 ICE DRIFT DATA FROM ARCTIC OCEAN BUOY PROGRAM.....	52
9.4 COMPARISON OF MODELS AND DATA.....	54
9.5 ICE DRIFT FROM SAR.....	57
9.6 ICE DRIFT FROM AVHRR IMAGES	62
10. ICE CONCENTRATION FROM SATELLITE DATA	64
10.1 RETRIEVAL OF ICE CONCENTRATION FROM SSM/I DATA	64
10.1.1 <i>Observation of brightness temperature</i>	64
10.1.2 <i>Algorithms for retrieval of ice parameters from brightness temperature</i>	64
10.2 EXAMPLE OF ICE ANALYSIS FROM SSM/I DATA.....	66
10.3 ICE CONCENTRATION FROM AVHRR DATA.....	70
10.4 ICE CONCENTRATION FROM SAR DATA.....	71
11. REFERENCES	73

1. Introduction and objectives

Sea ice areas are of vital importance for arctic marine ecosystems and in particular for the polar bears. Mapping of sea ice is currently performed at relatively coarse resolution by the ice service of DNMI, but these maps do not contain detailed information about ice processes and variability which are important for the marine ecosystems.

Polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) depend on sea ice for almost all aspects of their life. Monitoring the polar bear populations in the Svalbard and Barents Sea area is of high priority for the Norwegian Polar Institute. To develop a viable means of monitoring polar bears, it is essential to develop an understanding of how they use different habitats at different times of year. Reproductive failure and declines in population condition have been linked to changes in sea ice.

Developments in satellite telemetry applied to wildlife have provided one tool required to develop polar bear monitoring programs. Using Global Positioning System (GPS) technology and linkages to the ARGOS satellite system, high resolution (<100 m) location information can be obtained several times a day throughout the whole year. This technology has a much higher level of resolution both in the number of locations available per day and with respect to the spatial resolution of those locations. Example of such data are shown in Fig. 1.1. If the information on location can be coupled to detailed sea ice remote sensing using Synthetic Aperture Radar and other high resolution imagery, a new basis for monitoring can be created.

The main objective of this study has therefore been to develop a system for ice monitoring using satellite data with focus on processes and phenomena of importance for climate, marine ecosystems and transport of pollutants.

The specific objectives have been to:

- Identify sea ice parameters which can be derived from available satellite data and be used in a monitoring system
- Use these parameters to identify relevant indicators for climate change, effects on the ecosystem and on transport of pollutants as part of the monitoring under the Ministry of Environment's area 7 and 8
- Develop and adapt use of existing methods for automated mapping of identified parameters and indicators
- Develop and implement a GIS-based system for storage, integration, analysis and presentation of sea ice data, ARGOS/GPS data from polar bears and other relevant data
- Demonstrate practical use of the system over a limited period (spring 2001) in the Storfjorden area of Svalbard, followed by validation and evaluation.

Figure 1.1 Example of polar bear tracks in Storfjorden in April 2001 (Courtesy: NPI).

2. Review of satellite remote sensing methods and instruments

All remote sensing techniques for observation of the earth's surface use electromagnetic radiation in the visible/near-infrared (VNIR), thermal infrared (TIR) and in microwave bands of the electromagnetic spectrum. There are three principal measurement techniques applicable to ocean and sea ice observations:

1. Measurement of the part of the incoming solar radiation that is reflected at the surface of the earth (visual and near infrared remote sensing);
2. Measurement of the thermal radiation from the surface (infrared and passive microwave remote sensing); and
3. Measurement of the return signal from an active sources, especially microwave radar methods using several types of instruments which measure backscattered radiation from the surface.

The visible and infrared channels utilize intervals of the EM spectrum with high atmospheric transmission, such as in the optical bands from 0.4 - 2.5 μm , 3.5 - 4.0 μm and 10 - 13 μm . The EM waves in these intervals do not generally penetrate clouds, so remote sensing observations of the earth's surface in these bands can only be done during cloudfree conditions. This is a rather severe limitation because sea ice occurs in regions where clouds are present most of the time which inhibits regular observations of sea ice by satellite sensors operating in these bands. In the microwave area, at wavelengths above 0.3 cm, EM waves generally penetrate clouds which makes it feasible to obtain regular, daily observations of sea ice (Fig. 2.1).

Figure 2.1. The Electromagnetic spectrum with indication of the bands used in remote sensing.

2.1 BASIC REMOTE SENSING PARAMETERS

For a radiometer in the infrared or the microwave region, electrical and thermal properties of the surface will largely determine the basic parameter measured by the sensor. For a visual radiometer and in particular for a radar, the geometrical structure of the surface is often the most important factor. Some relations between surface parameters and the basic remote sensed parameters are discussed in this chapter.

2.1.1 ALBEDO

In the visual part of the spectrum, the albedo (or the reflection coefficient) is measured as a value between 0 (total absorption of the sunlight) and 1 (total diffuse reflection of the sunlight). Of the macroscopic sea ice components, new snow has the highest values of about 0.8. As the snow gets older, the albedo decreases to values equal to dry old ice of 0.6 or lower. For very old and wet surfaces of ice and snow, value can be as low as 0.2. Open water has even lower albedo, varying somewhat with incidence angles and wind. The vertical reflection coefficient of calm pure water is only about 0.02.

For snow and ice, the visual albedo decreases slowly with increasing wavelength. In near infrared, the decrease is more rapid for most snow and ice types, reaching very low values below 0.1 for wavelengths over 1.5 -2.0 μm . This low albedo can be utilized in the discrimination of snow/ice from clouds. This is a major problem in the visual part of the spectrum where snow and clouds often show a similar signal.

2.1.2 SURFACE TEMPERATURE

In the thermal infrared part of the spectrum, the surface signal expressed as the radiance received by remote sensing can be used as input to the Planck equation of radiation to find the surface temperature T_s if the emissivity e of the surface is known. For water, the value of e in the most used thermal spectral band of 10 μm -12 μm is very high and stable, about 0.99, and accurate measurement (to 0.1 - 0.2° K) of the water surface skin temperature can be made. Snow and ice also have high emissivity in this region (values not well known) and approximate temperature measurements (to 1 - 2° K) of the upper layer can be made.

2.1.3 BRIGHTNESS TEMPERATURE

The brightness temperature T_b provides the measurement of the passive microwave emission from the surface. The brightness temperature is defined by the real surface temperature T_s and the emissivity e by the relation $T_b = T_s * e$. Depending on the application, various methods can be applied to separate the two variables e and T_s . For the most frequently used frequencies between about 6 GHz and 90 GHz, the emissivity of both ice and water show large variations. While e

for calm water can be calculated quite accurately from the electric properties, the value and variation of ϵ for the various forms of ice and snow is less accurately known, and therefore often has to be empirically measured. Passive microwave instruments typically have very large resolution cells in which many different components of snow/ice/water are present. Multi-frequency measurements are widely applied in algorithms for determining the relative coverage (concentration) of the sea ice components and possible also of other parameters.

2.1.4 RADAR BACKSCATTER COEFFICIENT

For active microwave systems, the most important parameter is the backscatter coefficient, called sigma-0 (σ_0), which expresses a measure of the energy scattered towards the source of the radiation, at scattering angle of 180° . The backscatter coefficient and other related parameters are further discussed in chapter 6 dealing with SAR ice classification.

2.2 INSTRUMENTS AND SATELLITES

A selection of satellite instruments are described which are relevant for sea ice observation. All instruments are operating on satellites in polar orbits of 700 –800 km height, with nadir line describing a line between approx. 81N and 81S, 14 orbits per day. Most are sun-synchronous or nearly so. The actual instrument coverage depends on its pointing direction (incidence angles), the swath width, and the on/off scheduling. The spatial resolution varies with the instrument. For SAR it also varies with the basic processing, defined as the number-of-looks. A one-look image is very grainy (poor radiometric resolution). Increasing the look-number will decrease the resolution while smoothing the signal to increase its radiometric resolution.

2.2.1 RADAR INSTRUMENTS

ERS SAR is a C-band synthetic aperture radar. It has operated on ERS-1 satellite from 1991, and on the ERS-2 satellite from 1995.

- Pointing is to the right of nadir with incidence angles from 20° to 26° . Arctic areas up to 84N are reachable.
- Swath width is 100km. Resolution with standard 3-look processing to PRI images is 30m.
- Scheduling is made by ESA based on research and application requests.
- Maximum on-time is about 12% each orbit due to power constraints.
- Request for scheduling is made in advance. A freely selected number of the scheduled scenes can be purchased from TSS in real-time and from ESA in aftertime. TSS require only very short notice, as all scenes within station coverage are normally read down.
- TSS delivers LRI images with 100 m pixels using about 30 looks

Radarsat SAR is a C-band synthetic aperture radar that has operated on the Canadian satellite from 1995,

- Pointing is to the right of nadir with standard incidence angles from 19° to 48°, with possibility also of lower and higher values. Arctic areas up to about 87°N are reachable.
- Several Modes are possible, each with its defined swath with and incidence angle range, ranging from Fine Res.Mode with 50km swath up to ScanSAR Wide Mode with 500km swath. Resolution vary from 8m at 1-look Fine Res. to 100m at 4-look ScanSAR.
- Scheduling is made based on ordering of scenes through a Radarsat representative (TSS).
- Ordering can be made up to 1 -2 days in advance, but the price will be higher for short notice orders.

Okean SLR (side-lookiong real aperture X-band radar, RLSBO) operates on the Russian Okean satellites in the O1 series (launch of Okean O1 -8 in Aug. 1995).

- Inclination is 82,5° (direct orbit), thus the satellites are not sun-synchronous.
- Swath is 450km for each of two instruments looking right and left.
- Resolution is 1km in range, 2.5km in azimuth.
- Data may be obtained from Russian agencies (NPO Planeta, RKA).

Scatterometers has operated on several satellites in periods since 1978 (Seasat, ADEOS), current satellites are ERS-2 and QuickScat. Their main purpose is the measurement of ocean wind fields, but also the signal over ice can be used to map areas of different backscatter.

- Pointing is to the right at 20° -50° incidence for ERS, conical at 46° and 54° for QuickScat.
- Resolution is 50km for ERS, 7km x 32km for QuickScat.
- ERS data are available free from ESA and from IFREMER. QuickScat data are available from NASA.

ENVISAT is planned for launch in 2002 equipped with ASAR instrument with a number of different modes providing a swath coverage up to 400-km wide. The Alt-Pol data provides two images with different polarisation combination acquired simultaneously in space and time i.e. it can be regarded as a two-channel SAR (HH-VV, HH-HV or VV-VH).

2.2.2 PASSIVE MICROWAVE INSTRUMENTS.

DMSP SSMI has operated on the US semi-military DMSP satellites since 1987, presently P13, P14 and P15 are functioning. It has 7 channels of variable frequency and polarization. A similar instrument, SMMR with 10 channels, operated between 1978 and 1987.

- Pointing is conical about nadir, with fixed 50° incidence angle and a swath of 1400km. Areas up to 88°N are reachable.
- Resolution is variable with channel, from about 15 km at 85 GHz to 60 km at 19 GHz.
- Continuous operation, with readdown of global data at US stations within 1 -2hours.
- Free data can be transmitted by anonymous ftp from MSFC (Marshall Space Flight Center). Last week data up to a few hours before current time is available. Older data are available from NSIDC (National Sea Ice Center) on CD-ROM and from Internet.

2.2.3 OPTICAL INSTRUMENTS.

NOAA AVHRR has operated on the US TIROS/NOAA satellites since 1978, with at least two satellites operating simultaneously. Presently N12, N14 and N15 are operating.

- Pointing is symmetrical about nadir with a swath of more than 2500km, of which the center 2000km are most often used. All areas in Arctic are reached.
- Pixel size is about 1km at swath center, 2-3km at the edges. It has five channels from visual (0.5 μ) to thermal IR (12 μ). N-16 has an additional channel for snow-cloud discrimination.
- Operation is continuous, with real-time downlink of all data. TSS provides data within its station mask..
- Free quicklook data of degraded resolution (3km) are available from TSS in near-real-time. Subscription of full-resolution multi-channel data within a 1000km area centered on a specified position can be purchased. Also full-resolution all-channel data over the full swath can be purchased on CD-ROM (SHARP files).

Landsat TM has operated on the US Landsat satellites since 1984. Presently Landsat-7 is functioning, the latest instrument name is ETM+.

- Pointing is symmetrical about nadir with a swath of 190km. Areas up to 82°N are reachable.
- It has 7 channels from blue (0.45 μ) to thermal IR (12 μ). Resolution for each channel is 30m, except in thermal IR where it is 60m. Broadband visual (panchromatic) image with 15m resolution is available.
- Operation is continuous, subject to light conditions. European Arctic areas are imaged in the summer season, readdown in Kiruna. A range of image products can be purchased from Eurimage through its representative TSS. Price of one scene, all channels from Landsat-7 US archive is \$ 600.- Cloud-cover limit can be specified by the customer. Quick-looks may also be available.

SPOT HRV has operated on the French SPOT satellites since 1986. Presently SPOT 4 is functioning.

- Pointing is steerable to left and right of nadir at up to 27° incidence with a swath of 60km. Areas up to 83°N are reachable.
- It has 3 channels from 0.5μ to 0.9μ. Resolution for each channel is 20m, panchromatic image with 10m resolution is also available.
- Operation scheduling is made in France based on orders. Cloud-cover limit can be specified by the customer.

SeaWiFS has operated on the Orbview satellite since 1998. It is a narrow bandwidth imaging spectrometer with 8 spectral channels from 0.4μ to 0.8μ. Its main purpose is to measure ocean color, and to derive parameters for ocean biology. Its use for ice is uncertain.

- Swath width is 1500km and 2800km in two modes. Resolution is about 1km.

IKONOS was launched in September 1999 and has provided very high-resolution data since January 2000. The satellite has one panchromatic band with 1m resolution and 4 bands in the visible to near-infrared spectrum with 4m resolution (0.45-0.90μm, corresponding to the Landsat-bands 1-4). These may be obtained simultaneously, but at double price. The image swath width can be up to 11km, and data can also be purchased as stripes with a maximum width of 11km and length up to 1,000km. The satellite can perform both in-track and cross-track pointing up to 26°, and has a revisit frequency of 1-5 to 2.9 days (depending on resolution). The satellite orbit is sun-synchronous, with an inclination of 98.1°. Data over Nordic areas can be downloaded at Kiruna, Sweden and bought from Satellus. The price is 18-21 USD pr. km², with a minimum purchase order of USD 3,000. Acquisition must be ordered at least five days in advance.

The TERRA-satellite launched in December 1999 includes a.o. the **ASTER** (Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer) instrument providing data at three different spectral ranges, i.e. the visible to near-infrared (VNIR), shortwave infrared (SWIR) and thermal infrared (TIR), at a resolution ranging from 15 to 90m, 14 bands altogether. The satellite has potential for cross-track pointing of up to ± 24° in the VNIR range and ± 8° in the two other ranges. The image swath width is 60km. The TERRA spacecraft operates in a near-circular, sun-synchronous orbit with an inclination of approximately 98.2 degrees. The satellite is currently undertaking its calibration phase.

3. Data available for the project

3.1 SATELLITE DATA ACQUIRED IN THE PROJECT PERIOD

The satellite data provided for the project are listed in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 List of AVHRR and SAR images obtained from TSS

AVHRR			ERS-2 SAR			
Date	Sat.	Format	Date	Format	Date	Format
1999-03-28	N15	Sharp	1998-12-29	PRI	2001-01-15	LRI
1999-04-10	N15	Sharp	1999-11-25	LRI	2001-02-09	
2000-01-01	N15	Sharp	1999-11-28	LRI	2001-02-19	
2000-03-26	N14	Sharp	1999-12-14	LRI	2001-03-10	
2000-03-29	N14	Sharp	1999-12-17	LRI	2001-03-13	
2000-03-31	N14	Sharp	1999-12-30	LRI	2001-03-16	
2000-04-02	N14	Sharp	2000-01-18	LRI	2001-03-26	
2000-04-05	N14	Sharp	2000-01-21	LRI	2001-03-29	
2000-04-13	N14	Sharp	2000-02-03	LRI	2001-04-01	
2000-04-16	N14	Sharp	2000-02-06	LRI	2001-04-14	
2000-05-05	N14	Sharp	2000-02-22	LRI	2001-04-17	
2000-06-04	N15	Sharp	2000-02-25	LRI	2001-04-20	
2001-03-23	N12	Subim.ch2	2000-03-09	LRI	2001-04-30	
2001-03-26	N14	Subim.ch2	2000-03-12	LRI	2001-05-03	
2001-03-29	N14	Subim.ch2	2000-03-28	LRI	2001-05-06	
2001-04-01	N14	Subim.ch2	2000-03-31	LRI	2001-05-19	
2001-04-04	N14	Subim.ch2	2000-04-13	LRI	2001-05-25	
2001-04-14	N14	Subim.ch2	2000-04-16	LRI	2001-06-04	
2001-04-17	N14	Subim.ch2	2000-04-29	LRI	2001-06-07	
2001-04-20	N14	Subim.ch2	2000-05-02	LRI	2001-06-10	
			2000-05-05	LRI	2001-06-23	
			• LRI		2001-06-26	
			a) LRI		2001-06-29	
			2000-11-25	LRI		
			a) LRI			
			a) LRI			
			2000-12-14	LRI		

3.2 AERIAL PHOTOGRAPHS FROM STORFJORDEN

During two helicopter flights (06 and 23 April 2001) in Storfjorden, aerial photographs were taken by Geophysical Institute at University of Bergen and delivered to this study for use in validation of the SAR-derived ice parameters. A summary of helicopter flights and photographs is given in Table 3.2 and 3.3. Examples of aerial photographs are shown in Fig. 3.1

Table 3.2 Storfjorden Helicopter flight 06.04.2001

WayPoint	Latitude	Longitude	Time	Elevation [mt]	Photo ID	Bearing
1	78.04053	18.94935	10:00	1176	2	23
2	78.06654	19.00788		1268	3	23
3	78.10841	19.13847		1148	4	23
4	78.14993	19.24948		925	5	23
5	78.17984	19.33104		922	6	23
6	78.18958	19.35533		856	7	23
7	78.22418	19.45305		802	8	23
8	78.25222	19.55054		750	9	23
9	78.28105	19.62487		586	10	23
10	78.31573	19.71770		576	11	23
11	78.32356	19.73146		605	12	23
12	78.37698	19.88898		484	13	20
13	78.39201	19.93097		260	14	20
14	78.39844	19.95080		254	15	20
15	78.41174	19.99072		238	16	20
16	78.41653	20.00697		209	17	10
17	78.41969	20.01598		190	18	
18	78.42441	20.03015		186	19	
19	78.45277	20.18525	11:00	-4	station	
20	78.45259	20.18384		36	20	120
21	78.45259	20.18384		36	21	140
22	78.45259	20.18384		36	22	140
23	78.45259	20.18384		36	23	120
24	78.45259	20.18384		36	24	140
25	78.45259	20.18384		36	25	130
26	78.45259	20.18384		36	26	150
27	78.45259	20.18384		36	27	150
28	78.45259	20.18384		36	28	130
29	78.45259	20.18384		36	29	130
30	78.45259	20.18384		36	30	140
31	78.45259	20.18384		36	31	130
32	78.45259	20.18384		36	32	20
33	78.45259	20.18384		36	33	-20
34	78.45259	20.18384		36	34	60
35	78.45259	20.18384		36	35	30
36	78.45259	20.18384		36	36	50
37	78.45259	20.18384		36	37	10
38	78.45259	20.18384		36	38	0
39	78.45259	20.18384		36	39	90
40	78.45259	20.18384		36	40	220
41	78.45259	20.18384		36	41	240
42	78.45259	20.18384		36	42	250
43	78.45259	20.18384		36	43	250
44	78.45259	20.18384		36	44	250
45	77.71404	18.62551	13:00	8	station	
46	77.84261	18.61925	15:45	-4	station	
47	76.99495	19.05907	18:00	2	station	
48	77.03590	19.54296	19:30	-10	station	
49	77.71404	18.62551		8		
50	77.71404	18.62551		8		

Table 3.3 Helicopter flight 23. April 2001

WayPoint	Latitude	Longitude	Local Time	Elevation	Photo ID	Bearing
1	77 25.83	18 29.00	12:07	5000	45	137
2	77 24.19	18 34.80	12:08	5100	46	137
3	77 22.46	18 40.90	12:10	4600	47	137
4	77 28.70	18 46.70	12:11	3700	48	150
5	77 00.62	19 16.78	15:44	2300	49	175
6	77 06.00	19 16.77	15:45	2700	50	175
7	77 04.50	19 16.67	15:46	2600	51	175
8	77 03.20	19 16.54	15:47	2500	52	175
9	76 59.60	19 16.70	15:49	2300	53	175
10					54	175
11	77 59.60	19 30.70	19:58	3000	55	337

7. b)

c)

d)

Fig. 3.1 Aerial photographs no 45 (a) and no. 53 (b) were taken on 23 April 2001. Photographs no. 1 (c) and 5 (d) were taken on April 6. Time, position, altitude and bearing for the images are shown in Table 3.3 and 3.4. Courtesy: Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen.

3.3 COMPARISON OF SAR IMAGE WITH AERIAL PHOTOGRAPHS

Figure 3.2. Subset of ERS LRI image of 20 April 2001 in the area where in situ observations were made. The arrow indicates position and look direction of the image in Fig. 3.1a.

The time interval of 5 days between SAR and aerial photographs in beginning of April limits the possibility to make exact comparison, because the drifting ice moves and changes in surface conditions can occur. Even with a 3 – day interval in late April, only the most stable ice forms can be compared. The best example is the one shown in Fig. 3.1 a and Fig. 3.2 where the fastice

is assumed to be stable in the period. The flaw-line (between the fastice and the pack ice) is visible in both data sets. Both albedo (in the photograph) and the backscatter (in the SAR image) show large spatial variations which cannot be compared exactly unless careful in situ measurements are carried out. Well-defined features such as flaw lines, fractures and large homogeneous floes can in general be detected in both types of images.

3.4 DATA FROM OTHER EXPERIMENTS AND AREAS

The aerial photographs from Storfjorden give very limited possibilities to test and validate algorithms for ice parameter retrieval. Therefore, data from other experiments will be described as a supplement to the Storfjorden data in chapter 6 – 10.

.

4. Ice charting symbols and nomenclature

The description of sea ice parameters has been standardised by the Sea Ice Working Group of WMO (WMO, 1970, 1985) which has defined a nomenclature used by all institutions producing ice maps today. A summary of the most important ice terms are listed in Appendix A. The main ice parameters, which are described by WMO (1985) are;

- 1) Ice concentration: C_t
- 2) Partial ice concentration of different ice types: C_a, C_b, C_c
- 3) Age or stage of development: S_a, S_b, S_c
- 4) Form (i.e. floe size): F_a, F_b, F_c , etc.
- 5) Surface features (i.e. ridges), and
- 6) Motion

Figure 4.1 The WMO egg code.

C_t	Total concentration of ice in area, reported in tenths.
$C_a C_b C_c$	Partial concentration in tenths of thickest (C_a), second thickest (C_b) and third thickest (C_c) ice types with C_a , C_b and C_c 1/10 or more. If only one thickness type is present equals C and the second level is left blank.
$S_a S_b S_c$	Stage of development (age) of ice concentration reported by C_a , C_b and C_c .
$F_a F_b F_c$	Predominant form of ice (floe size) corresponding to S_a , S_b and S_c , respectively.
$S_a S_b$	Development stage (age) of remaining ice types. S_o if reported is a trace of ice type thicker/older than S_a . S_d is a thinner ice type, reported when there are four or more ice thickness types.

$F_a F_b F_c$		$S_a S_b S_c$		
Form of ice	Width	Stage of development		Thickness
0	Pancake	1	New	< 10 cm
1	Brash	2	Nilas	< 10 cm
2	Ice Cakes	3	Young	10-30 cm
3	Small floe	4	Grey	10-15 cm
4	Medium floe	5	Grey-white	15-30 cm
5	Big floe	6	First Year	> 30 cm
6	Vast floe	7	Thin First year/White	30-70 cm
7	Giant floe	1.	Medium First Year	70-120 cm
8	Fast ice	4.	Thick First Year	> 120 cm
9	Icebergs	7.	Old	
X	No Form	8.	Second Year	no
C	Ice in strips in which concentration is C	9.	Multi-year	Defined ranges
			Icebergs	

The WMO egg code provides numerical values for ice concentration, stage of development (thickness) and form of the ice (floe size) for more or less homogeneous areas of ice. For preparation of ice charts the egg code as well as different symbols are used to describe the ice conditions graphically on a map. Some ice services use the egg code, such as the US National Ice Center, the Canadian Ice Centre and the Danish Meteorological Institute's ice maps of Greenland waters. The Russian and Baltic ice maps use various other symbols, see Fig 4.2 The main problem of the WMO ice code is that it does not describe all the ice characteristics that are relevant for navigation and process studies which require mother detailed information. In countries where ice navigation is of major concern, the WMO code is supplemented by a number of other ice parameters.

The Baltic sea ice code

The countries surrounding the Baltic Sea including Norway do not use the normal WMO egg code in their ice maps, but a set of symbols that are consistent with the WMO standard nomenclature. The most important symbols are shown in Fig. 4.2

Figure 4.2 Description and explanation of the Baltic Sea ice symbols which are also used in the DNMI ice charts

An example of ice chart produced by DNMI is shown in Fig. 4.3. These maps include the Svalbard area, but the resolution of the maps is too coarse to identify ice processes in smaller areas such as Storfjorden. The use of SAR imagery, shown by the example in Figure 3.2, can improve the details of ice maps significantly compared to the DNMI ice charts.

Figure 4.3 Example of DNMI ice chart from 3 February 1997 which also contains spatially averaged sea surface temperature. The ice symbols are shown in Fig. 4.2 Copyright DNMI.

5. Processing of AVHRR data

5.1 RETRIEVAL OF SURFACE ALBEDO AND TEMPERATURE

The purpose of using AVHRR data is to compute and display surface Albedo and Temperature of ice / water in clear areas, based on available calibration data from NOAA and input files from TSS. TSS files in two formats are used, either 1) Swath-data in Sharp 1B, or 2) Subimage - 1024 data in tiff. Output are two raster images in Subimage 1024-Svalbard imf-format, with user-defined coding of pixelvalues to ch.2 Albedo and to ch.4 Temperature, and with the cloudy pixels masked using ch.3A Albedo.

Channel 3A data is only present from N-15 onward. This channel at 1.6 μ is able to separate snow / ice (low albedo) from clouds (high albedo), using an albedo limit value. From the satellite, signal from channel 3A will alternate with the channel 3B signal, Ch.3A is designed to be switched on when sun is above min. height and in high latitudes. Due to changes in NOAA operational routines, the 3A channel signal was unfortunately only available in N-15 in the period March - April 1999.

These images may be used subsequently for ice parameters such as ice-concentration, ice-type or ice-thickness. Albedo from channel 2 may be used for ice concentration in cloudfree areas when the sun is above a minimum height. Temperature from channel 4 may be used for ice concentration in clear areas when temperature is below a maximum value..

5.2 PROCESSING SYSTEM AND EXAMPLES

The AVHRR pre-processing program system in use at NERSC consists of the following individual programs:

Xalist, pb1 and pb2 are used for listing of Sharp-1B header data and computing a linear temperature calibration based on the in-satellite calibration system.

Ravh1c, cwindow and cimfix3 are used for reading the desired channels from Sharp-1B with conversion to 8 bits, and clipping or resampling to the desired 1024-format image.

Calbnor3 and linear-conversion are used for conversion to calibrated albedo (channels 2 and 3A), and to temperature (channel 4).

Clmask is used for masking of the cloudy pixels in the channel 2-albedo and the channel 4-temperature images.

Example of Subimage-1024 files are shown in Fig.5.1 (for channel 2-albedo) and Fig.5.2 (for the cloud-masked albedo). Since N-15 in April 2000 did not have channel 3A this mask has been simulated using a threshold in the channel 4-temperature. This alternative cloud masking procedure must anyway be used in the winter when channel 3A is absent.

Figure 5.1 NOAA-15 AVHRR channel 2 image of 13 April 2000 superimposed on a geographical grid

Figure 5.2 NOAA-15 AVHRR channel 2 image of 13 April 2000, with cloud mask (white pixels), using thresholding of channel 3A-albedo for masking.

5.3 DETAILS OF THE PROCESSING.

The following is a description of the run of the program system, with the use of a Sharp-1B format file or three Subimage-1024 format files as input.

For Subimage format files, go directly to Step 5. SHARP format files need to be processed from Step 1.

Step 1

- Mount the SHARP-formatted CD-ROM supplied by TSS. Start the program xalist, using the file LEADER as input, and list selected image header data: orbit, time, and coordinates of the node and the image center.

Step 2

This step calculates the accurate channel 4 temperature calibration, and also the Gain and Offset in an approximate linear calibration function.

- Start first the program pb1. Accurate data for internal blackbody and space temperature (in a 2-point calibration) are read from the IMAGE file.
- Start then the program pb2. This is menu-driven by Command no. 0 – 9. Com.0 displays the menu. Execute Com.1 to choose satellite (N-11 to N-14 is currently implemented) and channel (4 or 5). Com.2 ask for 4 PRT-counts followed by Com.5 that ask for 2 count values. These have been listed previously by program pb1. Conversion of 10-bit pixelvalue to temperature KT is computed using the non-linear basic equation (the Planck-equation) and the sensor-response curve. KT is a linear function of temperature equal to 500 for 0°C , with a gain of 10 bits per degC. It can be checked by Com.6, 7 and 8 if wanted.
- A linear approximation of the conversion with fixed Gain and Offset values are computed by Com.9. Here NP is the 10-bits pixelvalue.. For the scaling of NP to 8-bit (GOP)-values, a temperature-gain in degC per bit, and a temperature-offset (zero value) as the 8-bit value for 0°C , is chosen by operator. The resulting Gain and Offset in the resulting GOP-value equation is used as input to the temperature conversion equation in the following program (Step 3). Use of a linear equation simplifies the conversion procedure and is sufficient for most short time-interval, small temperature-range applications.

Step 3

- Read data from the IMAGE file into three separate imf-formatted swath-files, for channels 2, 3A and 4, using the program ravh1c.
- The out-file size can be chosen, the normal choice is the TSS standard size (2048x1440). An aggregation factor is chosen (every line, every second line, etc). Resampling of pixels along each line to an aspect ratio of 1.0 is made using a table for the reasmping from U (raw column no.) to T (resampled column no.). Transform type depends on the satellite height, which in turn is different for the two NOAA satellite series. TVXZ is the odd-numbered satellites up to N-11 and N-14, while UWYA is the even-numbered satellites up to N-12 and N-15
- The A-corner is the first pixel in the out-image, it can be chosen at a position different from start of the input- or raw-image, if wanted. A Skew-angle different from 0.0 is used for

images at lower latitudes (below 70°), and will compensate for the earth-rotation effect. No compensation is necessary in the Svalbard area.

- After selecting the channel, a choice if marking of shore&grid pixels (as supplied in the raw data by TSS) is wanted, can be made.
- Since the program converts the pixels from 10- to 8-bit values, a linear conversion defined by a Gain and an Offset suitable for the selected channel must be supplied. Choice of VNIR (Visual&NearIR)-calibration is implemented for N-14 and N-15 Ch.2 and 3A conversion (using available NOAA cal.data) to scaled %Reflection if no further processing is done. Otherwise a Gain of 0.5 (or 1.0 depending on pixelvalue-distribution) and an Offset of 0.0 can be used for these channels, as the calibration is done in Step 4.
- For Ch.4 and Ch.5 the Gain and Offset values calculated in Step 2 is used.
- The program is run for all the channels wanted by selecting 1 (yes) for another channel.
- The resulting swath-files of 2048x1440y are in an Oblique Mercator projection with satellite nadir as the centerline and the sensor basic linespacing (1.1km) as the pixelsize.

Step 4a

- A Subimage in the 1024-Svalbard format can be made by the program cwindow. Clip is defined by input of the column (x) and line (y) in the swath-file that will correspond to the “A-corner” 0,0 in the Subimage file. Note that the pixelsize and orientation is not changed by this routine.

Step 4b

- b) Alternatively, the Subimage can be extracted by a resampling-program. from the swath-file projection and pixelsize to a pre-defined projection (e.g. the “TSS Svalbard” polar-stereographic proj. with 78.5N, 16.0E at center, vertical 0°E meridian, and 1.0km pixelsize). The program cimfix3 can be used for this.

Step 5

- c) Conversion of Subimage Ch.2 and Ch.3A values to Albedo is made by program calbnor3. Note that the tiff-files from TSS first must be converted to imf-files using the program: bin2gop.
- d) The Subimage-format 8-bit values are first converted to the raw (the HRPT-format) 10-bit values, since the NOAA calibrations are given for these values.
- e) Channel 2 and 3A values are then converted to scaled Reflection factor (%), using available NOAA calibration equations on the 10-bit values. Equations are linear (single gain) up to N-14. From N-15, the 2-piece linear equations (dual gain) are used.
- f) Last, the Reflection factor is converted to scaled Albedo (%), using a sun-height normalising factor.
- g) The program needs input of date and time for sun height. Corners are inputted, alternatively the corners for Svalbard-1024 Subimages from TSS can be selected.
- h) Atmospheric correction is small for Ch.2 and Ch.3A and is neglected for these channels.

- i) The 10-bit values corresponding to 8-bit 0 and 255 follow from the Gain selected in Step 4, alternatively they are Min and Max values to be found in the .hdr -file for Subimage files from TSS.

Step 6

- b) For SHARP files, channel 4 values are converted to scaled Temperature in Step 3, using the linear calibration equation found in step 2 on the pixelvalues.. For TSS Subimage this step cannot be performed. As these data are presently not available in the .hdr -file, approximate values of the Gain and Offset must be used (e.g. as found from other Sharp format orbits).

Step 7

- b) The program clmask3 performs the cloud masking of the images of Ch.2 Albedo or Ch.4 Temperature. Cloudy pixels are set to a fixed Mask-value (e.g. 255) A suitable Limit value of channel 3A Albedo is chosen by the operator, and all pixels with a value of Ch.3A Albedo greater than the chosen limit are set to the Mask-value

5.4 EXAMPLES OF TEMPERATURE AND ALBEDO MAPS FROM AVHRR IMAGES

.

a)

b)

Figure 5.3 NOAA-15 AVHRR data from 28 March 1999, with cloud mask (pink pixels) showing ice-free areas only east of Svalbard. (a) Channel 4 with temperature and (b) channel 2 with albedo which is proportional to ice concentration

a)

b)

Figure 5.4 NOAA-15 AVHRR data from 10 April 1999, 0655Z, with cloud mask (pink). A) shows Normalised albedo (channel 2) and b) shows surface temperature (channel 4) in arbitrary scale.

Figure 5.5 Zooming in on Storfjorden. Subset of the April 13 2000 image shown in Fig 5.2 with cloud mask as white pixels.

Figure 5.6 AVHRR Channel 2 from 17 April 2001. Easterly winds have opened up polynyas in the eastern part of Storffjorden, on the west side of Kvitøya and Franz Josef Land.

Figure 5.7 Surface temperature in C° from 17 April 2001 based on AVHRR channel 4 data.

5.5 ICE FORMATION RATE, SALT REJECTION AND RELATED PARAMETERS

For studies of the rate of ice formation, and the related salt rejection rate, a calculation of the heat exchange between the surface and the atmosphere may be desired. Again, a uniform ice sheet within the pixel is assumed (no mixed-pixel). A simple model of ice growth versus air temperature is to relate freezing-degrees-days, T_f to ice thickness. Lebedev 1938 gives:

$$H(\text{cm}) = 1.33 * (T_f ** 0.6)$$

where H is ice thickness after T_f , this being defined as the sum over all days of freezing of average daily temperature, minus -1.5°C (the freezing point). This is a very simplified equation but simple to use, as only one input parameter is required. On the average, ice grows quickly first, then more slowly as its thickness increases. Alternatively, a model of heat transfer may be set up, e.g. as in (Lepparanta, ed., 1998). From this model of the snow-ice-water system, using atmospheric parameters (wind, temperature, radiation) as input, it is possible to compute ice formation rate, given the many ice and snow parameters. Here also, ice thickness H is of major importance, but also many other must be known, such as: snow thickness, thermal conductivity, specific heat, latent heat of fusion, radiation extinction coefficient, etc. (Wadhams 2000).

Subimages of AVHRR albedo and temperature for Storfjorden on 17 April 2001 are shown in the Fig. 5.8, while the ERS SAR classified image obtained on the same day but almost 3 hours earlier is shown in Fig. 5.9. First, consider the albedo image. Albedo is generally used as a measure of the ice concentration. The presence of snow-cover / bright-ice surface is used as defining the "ice" class, and the dark-thin ice types is classified in the "water" class. This is the usual method in making ice maps for ships, the results are quite accurate, as demonstrated in many expeditions. Alternatively, the dark surface of thin ice and water can be interpreted as small ice thickness, and the brighter surface as greater thickness. This may be desired for geophysical research, but the results are obviously much more uncertain. One reason is that the relation albedo-thickness is very variable (e.g. snowfall or frost flowers will quickly give high signal with the same ice thickness), and also very non-linear (even fully snow-covered, ice thickness will continue to grow). Its use for other purpose than ice concentration is therefore questionable.

Comparing the two images available from AVHRR: albedo from Ch.2 and temperature from Ch.4, they show a great similarity of details. This implies that the information from the temperature image is also well suited for ice concentration (the main difference is that the contrast ice - water is somewhat less than for the albedo). Further, the great similarity with the albedo image implies that the use of channel 4 temperature for heat flux measurements and possible other geophysical parameters can be relevant.

Figure 5.8.
AVHRR sub-image of the Storffjorden area on 17 April 2001: a) albedo image (channel 2), b) temperature image (channel 4). The rectangle shows position of ERS SAR image from 20 April

Figure 5.9
ERS SAR image classified into roughness categories: blue is the lowest roughness associated with open leads, red represents the highest roughness of sea found in the central part of Storffjorden, yellow is high backscatter from glaciers.

A comparison with the SAR image in Fig. 5.9 is also of interest. The fast ice boundary (flaw line) can be easily seen in all images. Also the open water (including thin ice and/or low ice-concentration) in the inner part of the fjord are comparable. South of 78N however, the pack ice image is very different on SAR, mostly caused by this sensors great sensitivity to rough ice. Most of the larger floes seen in the two AVHRR channels are also very difficult to find on SAR. In addition to roughness, the SAR sensitivity to ice salinity and the signal penetration into lower layers play an important role. For more quantitative work on these differences and their implication for the ice parameters, more comparisons with in-situ data, preferably simultaneous large-area maps / measurements, are required.

6. Use of SAR in sea ice classification

The most important active microwave remote sensing instrument for ice monitoring is the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) which provides high resolution images of the ice surface. In this chapter we first present some results of the SIZEX experiment (Seasonal Ice Zone Experiment) which was an ERS-1 SAR ice validation experiment in the Barents Sea in March 1992 (Sandven et al., 1999). Finally, we show results of the SAR ice classification in Storfjorden using data from 1999 – 2001.

6.1 GENERAL INTERACTION BETWEEN SAR AND SEA ICE

The radar backscatter from sea ice is highly dependent on physical ice properties such as salinity contents, temperature, surface roughness, snow layers and presence of water. Fig. 6.1 is a conceptual illustration of the interaction between active microwave and different types of ice such as sea ice including multiyear, firstyear (smooth and rough), open water without wind, glaciers and lake ice. Multiyear ice is characterized by low salinity in the surface layer (< 2.0 ‰) which allows penetration of the microwaves into the ice (volume scattering). Firstyear ice, on the other hand, has higher salinity in the surface layer (5 - 7 ‰) which causes mainly surface scattering. The volume scattering from the multiyear ice tends to give higher backscatter than the surface scattering from smooth firstyear ice. However, firstyear ice can also give higher backscatter due to rough surface caused by ridges, small floes with many irregular edges and snow crystals.

Figure 6.1 Schematic illustration of the interaction between radar microwaves and ice types (a) sea ice, (b) glaciers, ice sheets and lake ice.

Open ocean gives very low backscatter in the case of no wind, but usually there is some wind which causes short surface waves and high backscatter values (Shuchman and Onstott, 1990). In the SIZEX92 experiment some of these problems were studied in more detail.

6.2 SIZEX 92 ANALYSIS OF SAR IMAGES AND IN SITU MEASUREMENTS

During SIZEX92, C-band ERS-1 SAR images with VV-polarization were downlinked and processed at Tromsø Satellite Station and distributed to the Nansen Center for further analysis as well as real-time use during the field experiment. SAR backscatter values from several ice types and open water conditions were analyzed during the experiment. Each image was averaged from 16 x 20 m pixels to 100 m x 100 m pixels, thereby removing much of the speckle noise. The images were then normalized to incidence angle of 23° (in the center of the swath) by applying antenna pattern and incidence angle/distance corrections as described by ESA (Caneva, 1992). Finally, the pixels in the images were calibrated to σ_0 backscatter values by the relation $\sigma_0 = 20 \log V - 47.4$, where V is the digital value of the 8-bit images analyzed at the Nansen Center. The lowest backscatter observed in the images had values of $V = 14$ (grease ice) and this was assumed to correspond to the noise floor of - 24.5 dB. The accuracy of this calibration is estimated to be ± 1 dB.

The primary in situ measurements were profiles of snow and ice parameters taken at several sites from ships and helicopter. A total of 21 sites were investigated during the SIZEX experiment from March 2 to 11, 1992. At each site several ice cores were drilled to get obtain some spatial statistics of the ice parameters. The ice cores were analyzed for temperature, salinity, density and brine volume. Ice type was identified, ice thickness was measured and surface roughness was characterized. Snow thickness, temperature, grain type, grain size, density and layer description were also obtained at each site. An example of a SAR scene extending from open water to the interior of the ice pack is shown in Fig. 6.2a. From the SAR images and the in situ observations the ice conditions in this part of the Barents Sea could be divided into three zones, reflecting different signatures from different physical processes. In the following discussion each of these zones, which are denoted A, B and C, are described in terms of their SAR signatures

6.2.1 ZONE A: THE INTERIOR OF THE ICE PACK

In the upper left part of the SAR image in Fig. 6.2a many multiyear floes were found about 100 km into the ice pack. The backscatter value of these floes were typically -9.0 ± 1.5 dB. Between the multiyear floes areas of undeformed firstyear ice typically 2 - 3 m thick was observed. This ice had backscatter values from - 10 to - 13 dB. Refrozen leads with smooth thin ice had the lowest backscatter values, between - 19 and - 13 dB. Ridges and leads with open water were

found to have variable and higher backscatter, above - 8 dB. In the interior of the icepack the ERS-1 SAR demonstrated good capability to discriminate between: a) young ice in refrozen leads, b) multiyear ice in large floes, c) rubble fields/ridges, and d) smooth firstyear ice using simple thresholding of backscatter values.

6.2.2 ZONE B: THE SMALL FLOE AREA

This zone is characterized by small floes typically 10 - 100 m large, which have been broken up by surface waves penetrating from open ocean into the ice pack. The width of the zone depends on the intensity of the wave field in the preceding days. During the SIZEX experiment the zone was 20 - 30 km wide and was clearly identified in the SAR images as more uniform zone between open ocean and the interior of the ice pack (Fig. 6.2a).

Figure 6.2 (a) Upper figure is an ERS-1 SAR image from the SIZEX experiment (5 March 1992) , covering 100 by 100 km of the marginal ice zone with characteristic zones denotes A, B and C. (b) The lower figure is the result of the Wackermann classification of ice types and open water from the SAR image above. The colour code for the classification is: open water: blue, grease ice: grey, pancake ice: yellow, deformed firstyear ice: red, multiyear ice: green and undeformed firstyear ice: violet.

The dominant ice type is rough firstyear ice 2 - 3 m thick with backscatter values ranging from -10 to -6.5 dB. These values are significantly higher than for the undeformed firstyear ice in zone A due to the increased surface roughness. This surface roughness is caused by the edges and ridges of the numerous small floes which cannot be identified in the SAR images. During the experiment the ice concentration was generally high (> 95 %). The open water or thin ice areas between the floes was in the range of 1 - 10 m, which could not be observed in the SAR images.

Multiyear floes, which drift southwards with the East-Spitzbergen Current, could also occur in this zone. Similar to the firstyear floes the multiyear floes tended to break up due to the wave field. The SAR signature of small multiyear floes was similar to that of surrounding firstyear floes. Drifting icebergs with a horizontal scale of 100 m and a draft of 5 - 8 m were observed frequently in the zone, but their SAR signature even in full resolution images was diffuse. Reliable observations of these icebergs could not be made by the ERS-1 SAR.

6.2.3 ZONE C: THE AREA OF ICE FORMATION

Most of the ice in the Barents Sea is formed locally as the ice edge advances southwards during the freezing season. In the experiment the areas of ice formation were mapped by SAR images and documented by in situ observations. The first stage in ice formation is grease ice which dampens out the short surface waves and causes low radar return signals. This ice had the lowest backscatter of all ice types, ranging from below -24 to -14 dB. After 1 - 2 days of freezing the grease ice starts to form pancake ice with characteristic edges which causes high radar return, typically above -7.0 dB. As the pancake ice grows thicker during the winter it forms 1 - 2 m thick firstyear ice. The ice in this zone is constantly exposed to surface waves and is therefore characterized by a rough surface. Grease ice and calm water (wind speed below 3 m/s) can have overlapping backscatter values which makes the interpretation of the SAR images ambiguous, however no wind speeds below 3 m/s were observed in the experiment. Open water in the SAR images had higher backscatter than any of the observed ice types, from -4.5 to -3.0 dB. The backscatter values for the most important ice types in the Barents Sea is summarized in Fig. 6.3.

An automated ice classification algorithm developed for the MIZ has been applied to the SIZE92 data, an example of which is shown in Figure 6.2b. The image segmentation, where each region is assigned to a different ice type, was done using the *Wackerman and Miller* algorithm [1996]. Their goal is to eventually be able to reliably apply such an algorithm to any ERS SAR image acquired in the MIZ. The algorithm uses both statistics and texture (namely, measures of decorrelation and co-occurrence) to find the optimal separation between pixel classes. *Wackerman and Miller* [1996] found about 80% accuracy in their cases from the Barents Sea MIZ, mostly due to the statistics rather than the texture measures.

Figure 6.3. Backscatter coefficient for ERS SAR (C-band, VV-polarization and 23° incidence angle), expressed in σ_0 (left) and digital value (right), for different regions and ice types as observed during the SIZEX experiment and other SAR ice validation experiments. Note that ERS SAR backscatter for different wind speeds over open ocean are included for comparison because the SAR backscatter for open water can often be similar to some of the ice types (Sandven et al., 1999).

6.2.4 COMPARISON OF CLASSIFICATION BY SIMPLE THRESHOLDING AND TEXTURE ANALYSIS

In order to implement a simple and user-friendly classification method, it is recommended to use a simple thresholding method which is based on look-up tables of σ_0 values as shown in Fig. 6.3. This method requires calibrated images and is easy to implement, for example in a GIS system. A more sophisticated method, like the Wackermann algorithm, will usually give more reliable

classification results, but application of this method is more laborious. Figure 6.4 shows a comparison between the two classification methods, applied on the SAR image from 5 March 1992 (shown in Fig 6.2.a)

Figure 6.4 . Classification of the ERS-1 SAR image 5 March 1992, using a) thresholding of backscatter values, and b) texture analysis by Bogdanov (2000).

6.2.5 SUMMER CONDITIONS

The classification into three zones suggested for winter conditions would not be valid in the summer, because the interaction between radar microwaves and the ice surface is quite different from winter conditions due to the different temperature. Zone C with ice formation would be absent. Zone A and B would be detectable, but the discrimination between different ice types becomes less significant. Due to wet snow and melt water on top of the ice the SAR backscatter values from multiyear floes is reduced compared to the winter situation and becomes similar to the signature for firstyear ice. It is therefore difficult to separate the two ice types based solely on backscatter levels (Johannessen et al., 1992). Thin ice types such as grease ice, pancake ice and young ice are usually not found in the summer.

6.3 CONCLUSION FROM THE SAR ICE CLASSIFICATION STUDY

In the SIZE92 experiment ERS-1 SAR scenes of all the major ice types in the Barents Sea were analyzed for winter conditions. These include:

- 3 - 4 m thick multiyear ice floes which originate from the Arctic Ocean north of Svalbard.
- refrozen leads with smooth thin ice .
- consolidated firstyear ice 2 - 3 m thick which is formed between multiyear floes in the interior of the ice pack during the present winter season.
- rough ice in leads, ridges and rubble fields.
- first year ice 2 - 3 m thick in a 20 - 30 km wide zone inside the ice edge broken up in typically 10 - 50 m large floes due to wave action.
- new ice formed outside the ice edge (grease ice and pancake ice).

The most difficult factor which influences the SAR ice classification and ice concentration algorithms is the variable backscatter from open water due to the wind speed. Ice classification algorithms have been applied to the SAR images from the SIZE92 experiment, and the results from use of the Wackerman algorithm are shown in Fig. 6.2b and 6.4 (Wackermann and Miller, 1996, Bogdanov, 2000). Such classifications will normally result in ambiguities, because different ice types can have similar SAR signatures. Also open water can have similar signature to some of the ice types, in particular pancake ice and ice with rough surface. In order to improve the algorithm for ice type determination and thus also for the ice edge detection and ice concentration estimation, it is necessary to know the open water signature as a function of wind speed. The wind speed can thus be used as input parameter in the algorithms.

The main result of the SIZE92 program and other SAR ice investigations, (Johannessen et al, 1992), is improved understanding of ice processes and their signatures in SAR images. All the previous SAR ice studies have contributed to the establishment of look-up tables, such as in Fig.6.3, for many ice types at different seasons (Onstott, 1992). Although there are many phenomena and features observable in SAR images which remain to be explained, the general knowledge of SAR ice signatures is fairly well established.

6.4 SAR ICE CLASSIFICATION IN STORFJORDEN

Storfjorden is an active ice formation area during the winter due to the recurring polynya which forms during northerly winds, coinciding with low air temperature. Under such conditions the firstyear ice is pushed southwards, opening up the northern part of the fjord where new ice starts to form. In the early ice season, (i.e. December) the ice cover consist of new, young and thin firstyear ice (Haarpaintner, 1999). The surface properties of these ice types, which are important

for the SAR signatures, can change quickly. Therefore, SAR ice classification can be very unstable as shown in Fig. 6.5, where two SAR images with three day interval were analysed. In December, the ice in Storffjorden is mainly new and young ice which change its surface properties very rapidly. Under such conditions the SAR signatures changes too much for the ice classification to be useful. However, areas of open water and new ice (grease ice and frazil ice) can be identified by very low backscatter in cases with low wind. It is noteworthy the classification results over land is very stable, showing that the classification method is consistent for snow and ice surfaces which change very little in the period.

Figure 6.5. Time variability of SAR ice classification in Storffjorden in early winter between 14 December (a) and 17 December 1999 (b)

Later in the season, in April, ice conditions are more stable with respect to the SAR classification using the thresholding technique. In the SAR classification in Fig. 6.6, from April 13 and 16 2000, areas of rough first year ice (red areas) do not change too much in the three day period, but open water and thin ice areas (blue areas) change more significantly.

a)

b)

Figure 6.6 SAR ice classification in Storfjorden on 13 April (a) and 16 April 2000 (b) land contours are shown as white lines.

Examples of ice classification from April 2001 are shown in Fig. 6.7. Three passes were available with the usual 3-days interval, two passes with 2 scenes, and the pass in the middle (17.Apr.) with 3 scenes. The helicopter flight taking aerial photographs was made on 23.April

(Table 3.3). The land signatures are very stable, suggesting that classification is consistent over time for stable surfaces. Sea ice signatures, which can change more rapidly, varied spatially but were temporally consistent for the fast ice in a 5 –15 km wide along land. Its boundary (the flaw line) does not show well since the examples are processed for pack ice studies. On 14 April the ice is compressed in the north of Storfjorden, giving the high backscatter (red-yellow) of rough ice here with very little thin ice (blue). On 17 April some thin ice is formed as the ice has moved south about 50 km in the 3-day period (this ice drift is measured by SAR as shown in chapter 9). As the pressure is relaxed, the ice is now somewhat less rough (less yellow) in the mid-fjord. The image on 20 April shows a large area of thin nilas and young ice with low signal (blue) in the inner fjord, forming the well-known polynya that appears here with winds from north. Measured ice drift since 17 April is 10 –15 km southward, with the largest drift in the north part.

Figure 6.7 Classified ERS SAR images from Storfjorden on 14 (a), 17 (b) and 20 (c) April 2001.

6.5 COMPARISON OF SAR AND AVHRR IMAGES

Since SAR and AVHRR images have several complementary properties, it can be useful to observe ice processes with both methods when cloud conditions permit. In the example shown in Fig. 6.8 a small area in the outer Storfjorden including Sørkapp is mapped by both satellites on 13 April 2000.

Figure 6.8 An area of about 70 by 80 km in outer Storfjorden observed by a) albedo from AVHRR channel 2; b) temperature from AVHRR channel 4, and c) ERS-2 SAR.

Open water and leads are characterized by dark signature in all images. In AVHRR mages dark signatures represent low albedo (a) and high temperature (b). Open water in SAR have low backscatter in th ecase of low wind speed (c) but increases rapidly as soon as the wind speed exceeds a few m/s. Large floes (5 – 20 km) can be well detected in all images, but the higher resolution of the SAR images allows better identification of the smaller floes, especially when they are surrounded by open water/thin ice. When many small floes are grouped in clusters with no openings between, it can be difficult to identify in SAR images.

7. Study of ice ridges and leads in satellite images

7.1 REVIEW OF A PREVIOUS STUDY ON RIDGES IN BOTHNIAN BAY

7.1.2 USE OF FINE-RESOLUTION RADARSAT IMAGES

Since no dedicated study of ridges and leads were carried out in Storfjorden, we will review some results from a previous project in the Bothnian Bay (Sandven et al., 1999a,b). In this area a Fine-resolution RADARSAT image was obtained on 13 March 1997 to study ridges, level ice areas and the transition zone between fast ice and the drifting ice (Fig. 7.1).

Figure 7.1. Geolocated RADARSAT Fine-resolution image from 13 March 1997 in the Bothnian Bay. The line marked "A" indicates the border between the fast ice on the eastern side and the drifting ice on the western side. The red lines and polygons enhance the main ridges and features in the image used to determine the ice motion (indicated by the arrows). The white rectangle indicates the zoomed area shown in Fig. 7.2. The bold yellow line indicates where laser profiles were obtained by aircraft. Copyright: Canadian Space Agency / Agence spatiale canadienne 1997.

One-look resolution of the image was 8 by 8 m. Accurate geolocation has been achieved by assuming that the major ridges running north-south between 24°15' E and 24°30'E were stationary. Comparison of features in two consecutive images (10 and 13 March), obtained by laying them on top of each other in the image analysis system, shows that the ice west of the line denoted "A" running north-south in the centre of the image moved eastwards up to two km in three days, corresponding to a mean speed of 0.008 ms⁻¹. A more realistic impression of the information content in the Fine-resolution images can be achieved from Figure 7.2, where numerous floes and ridges can be identified.

Figure 7.2. Subimage of a RADARSAT Fine Resolution image, covering 12.5 by 12.5 km, as shown by the box in Fig 7.1. The image has pixel size of 12.5 by 12.5 m and is averaged from the full resolution image with pixels of 6.25 by 6.25 m. Copyright: Canadian Space Agency / Agence spatiale canadienne 1997.

7.1.2 OPTICAL IMAGES: AIRCRAFT PHOTOGRAPHS AND SATELLITE IMAGES FROM RESURS MSU-E

Optical data give a different, but complementary images compared to SAR images. Both aircraft images (Fig. 7.3 a) and satellite optical images (Fig. 7.3 b) were used to investigate the surface properties of ice during the field experiment in the Bothnian Bay in 1997. Since most of the ice in the Hailuoto area was snow-free, the optical images showed level ice to be dark. Ridges appeared bright due to the fact that snow had accumulated in the ridges because of wind accumulation in the previous days and weeks. Comparison between the optical image and the radar image shows very similar patterns of ridges (bright line features) and level ice areas. The MSU-E sensor is a multichannel high-resolution scanning imager onboard the Russian Resurs-01 satellite, providing images with resolution of about 40 m in 45 km wide swaths. A sub-image from the Hailuoto area is shown in Fig. 7.3 b.

Figure 7.3 a) Aerial photograph showing characteristic patterns of ridges and level ice in an area of about 1 by 1 km. Such photographs were used to validate observations from optical and radar satellites. Courtesy: J. Haapala. b) Subset of a Resurs MSU-E image covering about 15 by 15 km of the Hailuoto area, obtained on March 18 1997. The bold line (marked A, B, C) show the section where ridges were measured by aircraft laser altimeter, shown in Fig 7.4.

7.1.3 USE OF LASER ALTIMETER MEASUREMENTS OF RIDGES

Laser data were used in combination with satellite data to study the surface topography of the sea ice. Airborne laser profilometer measurements were obtained in the northeast sector of the Bay of Bothnia during the field experiment to quantify ridge sail heights and ridge density. Aerial photographs were obtained for identification of ridges, ice floes, ice types and snow cover. The photographs, in addition to the in situ observations, were used for validation of the satellite observations. Profiles of SAR backscatter, optical radiation and laser height measurements from an east-west section just west of Hailuoto are shown in Figure 7.4. The laser profiles show the ridge heights directly, while the satellite data also include the effect of rafting, snow cover and other small scale features at the surface. The highest ridges were about 1.5 m above a reference level. It is noteworthy that there is a qualitative agreement between the three types of data.

Figure 7.4 Example of profiles of MSU-E optical image from Resurs-01 (upper graph), RADARSAT SAR (middle graph) and airborne laser measurements (lower graph) taken in a 10 km long section just west of Hailuoto. The laser data are provided by Mikko Lensu. The horizontal axis is in meter, and the vertical axis is in cm showing the height measurements from the laser. The vertical scale of the satellite data is arbitrary. The horizontal scale is not exactly matched between the three types of data.

7.1.4 PRELIMINARY CONCLUSIONS ON THE BOTHNIAN BAY STUDY

For observation of ridges and other forms of rough ice, SAR images showed good capability to detect features. In situ observations were compared with SAR signatures showing that ridges as small as 20 – 30 cm can be detected in SAR images. But it is not yet clear to what extent quantitative measurements of ridges of different sizes can be obtained from SAR data. Airborne laser measurements were used to provide actual height and distribution of ridges, whereas SAR can mainly be used for mapping of areas with ridges and rough ice and discriminate them from areas of level ice. High-resolution optical images also showed good correspondence with the SAR images and could be used for mapping of ridge and level ice. The satellite remote sensing study has demonstrated capabilities and limitations of SAR images in local ice deformation and mesoscale ice dynamics. With more systematic sampling of SAR data, preferably every day during the ice season, it will be possible to analyze the ice dynamics in more detail and SAR data can play an important role in monitoring of the ice state.

7.2 REQUIREMENTS FOR OBSERVATIONS IN STORFJORDEN

No data have been available which can document the presence of ridges in SAR images in the Storfjorden area. One ERS PRI scene, with resolution of about 25 m have been obtained in the inner part of Storfjorden but this image was obtained early in the winter season (December), when the probability of finding ridges more than 50 cm high are small. A subset of the image is shown in Fig. 7.5.

The subset of the image was extracted west of Barentsøya where line structures were observed (Fig 7.5) indicating most probably leads of open water (dark features) between floes. The bright line features in the lower right corner could be rafted ice. Fig. 7.5 also shows a comparison between PRI images (25 m pixels) and LRI images (100 m pixels). For the size of the features in this image it is not a significant difference between LRI and PRI images.

Required data to observe and verify ridges in SAR images:

Based on experience from the experiment in the Bothnian Bay, it is recommended to obtain following types of data from Storfjorden or any other ice area where ridges are to be studied:

- documentation and maps indicating where ridges are most frequently occurring
- SAR coverage of these areas in late winter, preferable as a series of images of highest resolution
- Coincident observations by aerial photographs/video to document size and extent of ridges
- Airborne laser altimeter measurements coincident with SAR images
- Optional: high-resolution optical satellite image (SPOT, IRS, IKONOS, etc.)

Figure 7.5 Subset of ERS-SAR image (about 10 by 10 km) of the area just west of Barentsøya on 29 December 1998: a) LRI image; b) PRI image.

7.3 LEADS IDENTIFICATION IN SAR IMAGES FROM STORFJORDEN

Leads and polynyas are usually well-identified in SAR images and can be retrieved by ice classification methods. Examples of subimages from ice classification described in chapter 6 are shown below where several leads appear as blue signature due to the presence of open water or thin ice within the leads. The image from 13 April (Fig. 7.6 a) shows a well-defined lead separating the fastice along Spitzbergen from the drifting ice in the central part of Storfjorden. Three days later this lead is hardly visible in the SAR image (Fig. 7.6 b) due the compaction caused by easterly winds. In Fig 7.6 c and d leads are opening up in the northeastern part of Storfjorden in the period 14 – 17 April 2001. Experience suggests that leads narrower than the pixel size of 100 m can be identified, but detectability of narrow leads in SAR images has not been investigated.

7.4 LEADS AND POLYNYAS IN AVHRR IMAGES

As shown in chapter 5, AVHRR temperature as well as albedo images can identify leads and polynyas in Storfjorden and other areas when they are larger than the pixel size of 1 km.

8. Review of the possibilities to estimate ice thickness from satellite data

8.1. ICE THICKNESS FROM AVHRR DATA

If it is known that the pixels are fully filled with ice (of thickness H_i) with a snow cover (of thickness H_s), it may be possible to estimate H_i that is: ice thickness, from the satellite measured surface temperature, T_s . Ideally, a model of heat transfer from the water (at non-varying temperature – 1.5degC) through the ice and snow to the atmosphere must be set up. Also a model of the measured temperature T_s as a function of the vertical temperature profile together with the emission and absorption parameters in the snow and ice must be set up. Then these equations must be inverted to get H_i , assuming all other parameters to be known. This is theoretically feasible, but no reference to a practical use of this method has been found.

An alternative method is to use measured ice thicknesses and surface temperatures of representative ice/snow surfaces to derive at empirically determined relations between T_s and H_i . Here also, many parameters will be important such as air temperature and wind speed, snow thickness and density, and maybe others as well. A method for sea ice thickness mapping by IR satellite is described in (Loschilov 1999) and results are compared with Russian ice breaker measurements.

8.2 ICE THICKNESS RETRIEVAL FROM SAR

The possibility to retrieve ice thickness from SAR has been reviewed by P. Wadhams (Wadhams, 2000) suggesting three different approaches. Firstly, coincident profiles of SAR backscatter with aircraft laser elevation measurements gave positive correlation (0.51) where high backscatter corresponded to ridged areas which represent thicker ice. Furthermore, SAR backscatter profiles have been correlated with coincident submarine draft profiles, showing a better correlation of 0.68. Again, higher backscatter corresponds to thicker ice. It is clear that SAR backscatter alone cannot be used to infer the complete shape of the ice thickness probability density function, since less than half of the variance of the SAR backscatter can be explained by the draft variations. A different approach suggested by Kwok et al., (1999) uses a large number of SAR scenes to calculate ice types and ice velocity vectors for determining convergence and divergence fields, which are used together with a model to estimate growth and melt rates. In this way ice thickness distribution and its temporal evolution can be determined. The method requires systematic acquisition of SAR images throughout the ice seasons.

8.3 ICE THICKNESS RETRIEVAL FROM RADAR ALTIMETER

Analysis of radar altimeter over Arctic sea ice from ERS-1 and 2, Laxon and McAdoo (1994) have demonstrated a method to separate altimeter signals from sea ice and from open water (including leads and polynyas). By use of this separation method, and by averaging altimeter data over 100 by 100 km grid cells for each month of the year, it has been possible to measure ice freeboard. This is furthermore translated in to ice thickness by using the best possible relationship between freeboard and thickness. The altimeter-derived ice thickness estimates have been validated against available thickness data, such as submarine ULS data. The comparison in Fig. 8.1 shows agreement between the altimeter and submarine estimates of thickness to within ~0.5 m.

Figure 8.1 Comparison of ice thickness derived from radar altimeter ice elevation estimates and SCICEX submarine draft estimates from four different cruises. Courtesy S. Laxon, UCL.

In 2004, ESA will launch a new radar altimeter satellite, CRYOSAT, which will use a beam-limited altimeter to measure ice freeboard with higher accuracy and better coverage than ERS. CRYOSAT is the first satellite which will have global ice thickness measurements as a major mission objective.

9. Ice drift from satellite data

9.1 INTRODUCTION

The circulation of sea ice determines the advective part of the ice balance and provides a velocity boundary condition on the ocean surface. The spatial gradient of this circulation, also expressed as ice deformation, controls the abundance of thin ice and therefore the many surface processes dependent on this thin ice, such as turbulent heat flux to the atmosphere and salt flux into the ocean. Convergent ice motion increases the local ice cover mass by rafting and ridging. Sea ice motion is readily observed in satellite imagery, the scale of the observed motion being dependent on the spatial resolution of the imagery. In recent years a number of procedures have been developed to recognize common features in various types of sequential images to obtain displacement measurements (i.e. Kwok et al., 1990, Holt et al., 1992). The quality of these measurements depends more on geometric fidelity and image resolution than on physical understanding of the ice signatures themselves. Imagery acquired by SAR and AVHRR are of particular importance, SAR because of its high resolution and all-weather capability and AVHRR because of its large coverage and frequent repeat over sea ice areas.

9.2 ICE DRIFT FROM SSM/I DATA

It has recently been demonstrated that sequential imagery from the 85 GHz Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I) can provide ice motion observation in spite of the 10 km or more footprint (Liu et al., 1998). Also the 37 GHz channel can provide ice motion information (Kwok et al., 1998) when combined with SAR-derived motion and buoy measurements. SSM/I data are particularly useful for estimating the large-scale ice drift in the winter periods (Martin and Augstein, (2000) and complement the drifting buoys which only measures ice drift in parts of the Arctic Ocean. Martin and Augstein (2000) used a box size for data averaging of 87.5 by 87.5 km (7 by 7 pixels) in order to obtain a time resolution of 3 days in the velocity estimates.

Example of a 3-day ice drift map for the Arctic ocean is shown in Fig. 9.1. By combining ice drift from SSM/I data and ice thickness from ULS data it is possible to calculate ice volume fluxes, as shown by Drinkwater et al (2000) in the Weddell Sea and Kwok and Rothrock (1998) in the Fram Strait. An example of SSM/I-derived ice drift vectors in the Svalbard area is shown in Fig. 9.2.

9.3 ICE DRIFT DATA FROM ARCTIC OCEAN BUOY PROGRAM

A set of automatic data buoys which measure basic meteorological data such as atmospheric pressure, air temperature and buoy location are deployed in the Central Arctic Basin and its marginal seas. The data are transmitted via ARGOS. The programme was established in early

1979 by the Polar Science Center (PSC), University of Washington, USA. There are on average of 15 buoys in service at the time. The basic data sets consist of 12-hourly pressure and temperature fields (data set A and B) which represents 20 –30 Mbyte over a year. In addition there are 12-hourly buoy positions and interpolated ice velocity fields (data set C and D). Digital data sets are available from <http://iabp.apl.washington.edu/> via anonymous ftp as well as on tape from NSIDC.

Figure 9.1 Optimally interpolated ice velocity field for the three-day period 8-11 April 1993, using SSM/I data in combination with drifting buoys (circles with arrows). The velocity data are produced by The Polar Remote Sensing Group at JPL, California Institute of Tehnology

Figure 9.2 Example of SSM/I derived ice velocities in the Barents Sea area using the 85 GHz channel. The data are from 3 – 4 March 2000. . Courtesy L. Toudal, DTU

9.4 COMPARISON OF MODELS AND DATA

The mean ice drift fields are calculated for the periods when observation data are available for the whole Arctic Ocean from SSM/I data, analyzed by Martin and Augstein (2000) for the winters of 1987-88 and 1994-95. An example of a mean 3-day ice velocity field from SSM/I data is shown in Fig. 9.1. The mean simulated ice drift by the viscous-plastic model for the two winter periods studied by Martin and Augstein (2000) is shown in Fig. 9.3. This figure indicates the main features of the Arctic ice drift such as the Beaufort gyre, the Transpolar Drift, and the outflow through the Fram Strait. In order to obtain a quantitative comparison between models and data, correlations have been calculated between both horizontal components of the simulated and observed velocities, using all available buoy and SSM/I data. The correlation has been done for

different averaging periods, from 3 to 50 days, showing that the correlation increases with longer averaging time.

Figure 9.3 Mean simulated ice drift by the viscous-plastic model for the winters of 1987/88 and 1994/95. The axes indicate the model grid. (Kreyscher et al., 2000).

The highest correlation is found for the viscous-elastic model, reaching 0.80 for correlation with drifting buoys, and up to 0.90 for correlation with SSM/I data. The more uniform spatial and temporal distribution of the SSM/I data compared the IABP buoy data gives higher correlation for the former data. The lowest correlation is found for the free-drift model, with a correlation of about 0.70 and 0.80 for buoy and SSM/I data, respectively. Kreyscher et al (2000) have studied the ice export through the Fram Strait specifically, The north-south component of the ice drift through the Fram Strait, derived from SSM/I data and the viscous-elastic model, are shown in Fig. 9.4 a and b for the two winter periods 1987-88 and 1994-95.

Figure 9.4 Comparison of the northward drift velocities in the Fram Strait: a) and b) are time series of averaged 3-day velocities for the viscous-plastic model and the SSM/I observations; c) and d) are time series of monthly averaged velocities for all models and the observations (Kreyscher et al., 2000).

A significant temporal variability is found for these periods, using 3-day averaged data. The model is capable of reproducing the temporal variability quite well, at an RMS error of about 4 cm s^{-1} . Comparison between the models using monthly averaged data and corresponding data from SSM/I is shown in Fig. 1.12 c and d. The observed drift is best reproduced by the viscous-elastic model and poorest by the free-drift model, which systematically underestimated the drift.

By combining ice drift and ice thickness data, the ice volume flux through the Fram Strait can be calculated. All ice models except the free-drift model show a mean volume flux of about 0.09 Sv for the period 1979 - 1995, which is in good agreement with the results published by Vinje et al (1998).

The overall result of the model intercomparison shows that the viscous-plastic model yields the most realistic simulation, and that the free-drift model gives the largest errors. The compressible Newtonian fluid cannot prevent excessive ice thickness build-up in the central Arctic and overestimates the internal forces in the Fram Strait. Because of the lack of shear strength, the cavitating-fluid model shows marked differences to the statistics of the observed ice drift and ice thickness pattern.

9.5. ICE DRIFT FROM SAR.

SAR images of 100 – 500 m pixel size are well suited for calculating ice displacement vectors, if the time interval is appropriate for recognition of the same ice features in the two images. These features are commonly found as the larger ice floes, leads and other ice forms that are recognizable as being the same in the both of the images.

The Maximum Cross Correlation (MCC) algorithm implemented at NERSC and used since 1988 have been used. See Appendix A for a description. If displacements are generally large and in the same direction, the algorithm requires a displacement initial-value (found manually), for optimum performance. Also masking of land and other fixed features like fast ice can be done before the calculation starts to reduce the computation time (vectors in masked areas are not computed by the algorithm). Calculated vectors are filtered by choosing a lower limit for the correlation factor of the approved vectors. These vectors can be plotted on a blank map, or on top of one of the SAR images.

Example of the results for a rapid ice drift situation at the ice edge is shown in Fig.9.5. Here, the 10 hours interval from a descending –ascending pair of Radarsat passes was found to be suitable for the calculation. In Fig.9.6 to Fig.9.8 are shown examples for the Storfjorden area. Here, a 3 days interval are available for two ERS descending passes with a swath overlap of 68km at 77°N. The initial displacement and the correlation limit used for the calculations are given for the examples. Since displacements at various locations are often much more varied in the Fjord than in the more open ice areas of Fig.9.5, a greater number of erroneous vectors, e.g. as seen in the North part in Fig.9.6, is not unexpected. The algorithm performs better in the two other situations where motion is more uniform.

Ice motion derived from RADARSAT SAR images

Data from the Svalbard region, March 29 and March 29, 2000.
Vectors with correlation factor ≥ 0.3 are plotted.

RADARSAT SAR 29 March 2000, 04:36:00

Original Data © RSI/ISS 2000. Image Analysis NERSC.

Figure 9.5 Ice drift estimated in the Hopen area using two ScanSAR images (300 by 300 km) from 29 March 2000 at 05:36 GMT (image above) and 15:33 GMT. The NERSC ice kinematics algorithm has been used and vectors with correlation factor above 0.3 have been plotted.

Ice motion derived from ERS-2 SAR images

Data from the Svalbard region, April 13 and April 16, 2000.
Manually found vectors are plotted.

ERS-2 SAR 13 April 2000, 10:55:22

Original Data © ESA/ISS 2000. Image Analysis NERSC.

Figure 9.6 Example of ice drift in Storffjorden derived from ERS SAR images on April 13 and 16, 2000, during calm conditions.

Figure 9.7 Example of ice drift in Storfjorden during northerly winds, from 29 March to 1 April 2001. Vectors with correlation above 0.3 are plotted. Initial displacement of 44 km south and 10 km west was input to the algorithm.

Figure 9.8 Example of ice drift in Stor fjorden during moderate northerly winds, from 17 to 20 April 2001. Vectors with correlation above 0.3 are plotted. Initial displacement of 7 km south and 2 km west was input to the algorithm.

9.6 ICE DRIFT FROM AVHRR IMAGES

AVHRR images of 1km pixelsize are also well suited for ice displacement vectors calculation by the MCC method in clear weather. These images are available several times per day and each cover a large area with usually good overlap. However, the requirement of clear weather often drastically reduces the number of images suitable for ice motion analysis in a smaller area. Land, open ocean and heavy clouds areas are generally masked before the calculation starts. An example of ice drift vectors from AVHRR images is shown in Fig.9.9, which covers the same 3-day period as used for the SAR example in Fig.9.8.

Figure 9.9 Ice drift estimated from NOAA AVHRR images on 17 and 20 April 2001 during fairly cloud-free conditions in the Svalbard area.

Three days is generally a too long interval to obtain the best results for AVHRR, since the changes of ice forms can be quite large in 3 days. About 60% of the displayed vectors are in good correspondence with manually found reference values. Many of the erraneous vectors can be caused by the clouds covering the ice in various positions in the two images. In this case, clouds were not masked before running the algorithm.

10. Ice concentration from satellite data

10.1 RETRIEVAL OF ICE CONCENTRATION FROM SSM/I DATA

10.1.1 OBSERVATION OF BRIGHTNESS TEMPERATURE

The microwave brightness temperature T_b of the Earth's surface depends on the electrical properties of the surface, embodied in its emissivity e and the physical temperature of the radiating portion of the surface T_s . This may be expressed by the following relation in terms of the wavelength λ and polarization p :

$$T_b [\lambda, p] = e[\lambda, p] T_s \quad (10.1)$$

This relationship is true only for e and T_s independent of depth, a typical assumption for sea ice (Steffen, et al., 1992). The radiative transfer equation is the basis for the development of algorithms that convert the satellite radiance data into geophysical parameters. The microwave radiances received by the satellite are composed of various contributions from the Earth, atmosphere and space and are illustrated schematically in Fig. 10.1. The radiation received by the satellite, which is a function of wavelength and polarization, can be expressed by the equation:

$$T_b = e T_s e^{-\tau} + T_{up} + (1-e)T_{down} e^{-\tau} + (1-e) T_{sp} e^{-2\tau} \quad (10.2)$$

where T_b , T_s , e are as before, and $e^{-\tau}$ represents atmospheric absorption, T_{up} is the atmospheric upwelling radiation, T_{down} is the atmospheric downwelling component, and T_{sp} is the cosmic background component, as illustrated in Fig. 10.1. (Swift and Cavalieri, 1985).

10.1.2 ALGORITHMS FOR RETRIEVAL OF ICE PARAMETERS FROM BRIGHTNESS TEMPERATURE

There are several algorithms for estimation of sea ice concentration from brightness temperature observed in several channels and both polarizations (Steffen et al., 1992). An example of such algorithm is the NORSEX-85H which is an extension of the NORSEX algorithm developed by Svendsen et al. (1983) based on the SMMR data available from 1978 to 1987. 85H means that the extended version takes advantage of the improved spatial resolution of the 85 GHz channels provided by the SSMI system which is currently in operation.

The basic algorithm was developed after the NORSEX marginal ice zone experiment near Svalbard in 1979 conducted by the NORSEX Group (1983). The algorithm computes area concentration of total ice and two ice types: multiyear ice (MY) and first-year ice (FY). Two

The NORSEX algorithm requires that input brightness values are adjusted with a few degree K give 100% water over calm open polar water. These adjustments are made based on a few suitable scenes where the state for the atmosphere and the surface is known, and thereafter kept largely unchanged. Adjustments are different for SMMR and SSML.

A rough estimate of the average surface air temperature over 100 % packice from climatological data is used as input for each scene. The NORSEX algorithm output is % Water, % FY-ice and % MY-ice with a spatial resolution of approximately 60 km for SSML. 60 km is the resolution of the 19 Ghz channel. The 85 GHz channel, H polarization, (85H) is very sensitive to the difference between water and FY-ice as well as to the atmosphere. This channel is used to sharpen the ice-water boundary in the following way: The 85H is spatially lowpass filtered to the 18V/37V algorithm resolution of 60km. Concentration values are then multiplied with the ratio of the 85H-signal to the lowpass-filtered 85H-signal. This results in an image with a spatial resolution of 15 - 20 km, given by the 85H-signal, and with ice concentration values given primarily by the basic NORSEX algorithm.

The NORSEX-85H algorithm was developed for use under the SIZEX'92 experiments in the Greenland and Barents Sea (Sandven et al., 1999). The ice edge defined by the 30 -50% contour lines compares favorably with the ice -water boundary seen in near-simultaneous SAR images both under SIZEX'92 and later field experiments.

10.2 EXAMPLE OF ICE ANALYSIS FROM SSM/I DATA

The most common ice analysis using SSM/I data is to calculate total ice concentration by an algorithm as described in the previous section. An example of ice concentration map is shown in Figure 10.2. The data has been received on file in the form of geolocated brightness temperatures, and the required channels have been resampled onto a raster with 12 km spacing. On this raster, ice has been computed using the NORSEX algorithm and thereafter sharpened by using the channel 85H signal as explained above. Then a contouring algorithm has been applied to plot the 20%, 50% and 80% isolines for concentration. The map has been produced on the same day as the satellite measurements were obtained, 27 September 1997, by transferring data from the SSM/I data distribution service in USA. The SSM/I data are used for daily ice monitoring all over the world.

The most direct, quantitative means to study the global sea ice cover are satellite passive microwave remote sensors. Sea ice time series derived from multi-channel passive microwave data are among the longest continuous satellite-derived geophysical records, extending over two

decades. The Nimbus-7 Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) provided data from 1978-87, and the follow-up Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I) onboard Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) satellites has provided data since 1987. The 25 x 25 km gridded data sets are issued by the National Snow and Ice Data Center (USA). The brightness temperature data are used to calculate total ice concentration (the percent of ice-covered ocean within an image pixel), from which total ice area (the area of ice-covered ocean) and total ice extent (the area within the ice-ocean margin) are derived.

Figure 10.2 . Example of ice concentration map derived from SSM/I data in the Svalbard area. Isolines for 20 %, 50 % and 80 % ice concentration are drawn. Open water is defined to be areas with less than 20 % ice.

Analysis of SMMR and SSM/I records taken separately revealed a greater reduction in Arctic sea ice area and extent during the SSM/I period (Fig. 10 a,b). The decreases from 1987-94 were ~4% per decade compared to ~2.5% per decade from 1978-87 (Johannessen *et al.*, 1995), with no significant trends found in the Antarctic. Since then, merged SMMR-SSM/I time series have been produced and analyzed, establishing the trends more firmly. Bjørge *et al.* (1997) established the trend in Arctic ice area and extent (1978-95) to be about $-0.3 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ per decade (Fig. 10.3 a and b), corresponding to ~3% per decade, with no significant change in the Antarctic. The 3% per decade decrease in the Arctic ice extent (1978-97) was subsequently corroborated in a separate analysis (Cavalieri *et al.*, 1997) that also confirmed the hemispheric asymmetry seen earlier (Johannessen *et al.*, 1995; Bjørge *et al.*, 1997). Cavalieri *et al.* (1997) found a slight (~1.5%) increase in the Antarctic, which may be considered significant. The hemispheric ice covers fluctuate quasi-periodically, with predominant periods between 3-5 years, though their variability is apparently not correlated (Cavalieri *et al.*, 1997).

The capability to monitor interannual variations in multi-year ice area from SMMR and SSM/I data has recently been exploited using winter data, when first-year and multi-year ice signatures permit their distinction. The analysis revealed a relatively large (~7% per decade) reduction in the multi-year ice area 1978-98 (Figure 10.3 c), compared with an ~2% per decade decrease in the total ice area in winter (Johannessen *et al.*, 1999). This finding is supported by a SMMR-SSM/I data analysis that found an 8% increase (5.3 days) in the length of the sea ice melt season in the Arctic from 1978-96 (Smith, 1998). It is also corroborated by spatially- and temporally-fragmentary observations (from submarine sonar transects) of ice thickness decreases, as well as oceanographic data that have revealed changes in Arctic water masses since the 1970s that are reasoned to stem from a substantial (~2 m) melting of perennial MY ice. If this trend were to continue, it could eventually lead to a markedly different sea ice regime in the Arctic, altering heat and mass exchanges as well as ocean stratification.

Figure 10.3. Time series of Arctic ice area derived from SMMR and SSM/I satellite passive microwave data: (a) is monthly mean and (b) anomalies ice area in 1978-95 where the linear regression indicates a $\sim 31,000 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ decrease, corresponding to $\sim 3\%$ per decade (Bjørge et al. 1997). (c) is the fraction of multi-year (i.e., having survived the summer melt) sea ice area in winter (November-March), 1978-98, where the linear regression indicates a $\sim 30,000 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ decrease, corresponding to $\sim 7\%$ per decade (Johannessen et al., 1999)

10.3 ICE CONCENTRATION FROM AVHRR DATA

Ice concentration is estimated as the fraction of ice within a pixel assuming that any areas of bare ice with low albedo are negligible. For snow-covered ice albedo is generally able to separate well between water and ice.

Water has a channel-2 albedo, A_{2w} of approximately 5 -10%, while snow covered ice has an albedo value, A_{2i} that is normally in the range 60 –80%. The area-fraction, F_a of snow-covered ice to water within a pixel is linear related to the albedo, A_2 found from channel 2:

$$F_a = (A_2 - A_{2w}) / (A_{2i} - A_{2w})$$

In air temperatures appreciably below 0°C, a temperature difference is present between the water temperature, T_w (approximately -1 °C for sea-water) and the ice surface temperature, T_i . For thicker ice, T_i can be considered equal to the air temperature. The fraction F_t of thicker ice to water within a pixel is linear related to the surface temperature, T_s found from channel 4:

$$F_t = (T_s - T_w) / (T_i - T_w)$$

Bare ice will have a lower albedo than 60%, and thinner ice will have a higher temperature than the air temperature. If it is known that F_a and F_t equals 1 (the pixel is without water), the type(s) of ice within the pixel may be computed, otherwise bare ice and thin ice will lead to increase in the error of F_a and F_t .

Pixels with clouds must be filtered out before these equations are used for computing surface properties, since even thin clouds may obscure the surface in all channels.

Ice concentration is usually required as a mean value over a grid cell, for example 10 by 10 km, by averaging the estimates from all pixels within the grid cell. Alternatively, each pixel can be marked as either water or ice using a threshold value. Ice concentration is then estimated by the sum of all ice pixels. The difference between these methods will depend strongly on the nature of the error sources such as the amount of mixed pixels and the area of surfaces with intermediate signals, especially due to thin ice.

10.4 ICE CONCENTRATION FROM SAR DATA

Ice concentration is one of the key quantitative parameters, important for ice navigation, which can be derived from Radarsat ScanSAR images at a significant higher resolution than SSM/I ice concentration maps. Several investigators have suggested methods for retrieving ice concentration from SAR images (Dokken *et al.*, 2000), but there is not yet established standard algorithms which are widely used. Especially during summer conditions when the ice surface is wet from melting and can be difficult to distinguish from open water, it is a challenge to develop reliable algorithms for retrieving ice concentration from SAR data.

A method to estimate total ice concentration in the ScanSAR image of September 7 1997 have been tested using input from SSM/I observations of the same day (Sandven *et al.*, 2001). The first assumption of the method is that a threshold value separating ice from open water in leads in the ice-cover can be found in a SAR image without absolute calibration. However, range-correction must be in place to secure that the water-ice discrimination is possible across the whole image using the same threshold value. It is well known that with increasing wind speed the SAR backscatter of open water rapidly attains higher values than for ice. The next assumption is that within the ice-cover water pixels will have a lower backscatter value than ice pixels, at least for the images analyzed in this study. However, sufficient high winds can occur in leads to generate higher backscatter than for the ice types. In such cases the method also need to use an upper threshold to discriminate high backscatter open leads from ice with lower backscatter. Close to the ice edge and within leads and polynyas the assumption that a lower and upper threshold can discriminate water from ice can also fail. Such areas can nevertheless easily be identified in the SAR image and then masked out.

The pixel size of the original ScanSAR image was first reduced from 50 m to 500 m in order to reduce the speckle noise. After all land areas had been removed from the image, open water regions were determined and masked out using ice concentrations estimated from SSM/I, obtained by the updated NORCSEX algorithm (Svendsen *et al.*, 1983). A threshold of 20% ice cover was used for this operation. By analyzing the histogram of the remaining SAR-pixels two distinct peaks were found, assuming to correspond to ice and water areas, respectively, within the ice-cover. The pixel-value at the local minimum between the two peaks was chosen as the threshold value for separating the two surface types. In the next step all pixels with value above the threshold was set to 100 and all other pixels to 0, i.e. 100% or 0% ice concentration. Using SAR data ice concentration could be estimated over a certain unit area, defined by n by n pixels (Fig. 10.4) . The ice concentration was thus estimated at a resolution of 6.5 km, simply by computing the average mean over 13 by 13 pixels.

a)

b)

Fig 10.4 Ice concentration analysis of the ScanSAR image of September 4 1997 (a), presented with a spatial resolution of about 6 km.; (b) ice concentration estimated from SSM/I data on the same day using the NORSEX algorithm (Svendsen et al., 1983) with the 85 GHz channel. The area covered by the SAR image is marked by the square.

The results of the analysis of the SAR image of September 7 is shown in Fig 10.4 a, while the SSM/I concentration for the same day is shown in Fig. 10.4 b. The figure shows that ice concentration can be mapped in detail with SAR data, while the SSM/I data will smear out all details less than 10 – 20 km (Sandven et al., 2001).

One aspect of a simple thresholding procedure is the fact that newer ice types such as grease ice, nilas and gray ice also have relatively low backscatter signatures (Sandven *et al.*, 1999), similar to calm open water. This means that in several cases these ice types will be classified as open water, and as a result the ice concentration will be estimated only on the basis of firstyear ice and other ice types with backscatter signatures above the threshold value (including ridged young ice). For many practical purposes, including navigation and estimation of heat flux, this is not a severe drawback. Nevertheless, quantitative analysis should be carried out in order to assess the performance of various SAR ice concentration methods.

11. References

- Bjørgero, E., O. M. Johannessen and M. W. Miles, 1997. Analysis of merged SMMR/SSMI time series of Arctic and Antarctic sea ice parameters. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 24, 413– 416.
- Bogdanov, A.V. "Automatic classification of Synthetic Aperture Radar images of sea ice". Ph.D. thesis, St. Petersburg State University and Nansen International Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Russia, June 2000.
- Caneva, N., ERS-1 SAR calibration, Frascati, October 1, 1992.
- Cavalieri, D.J., P. Gloersen, C.E. Parkinson, H.J. Zwally and J.C. Comiso, 1997. Observed hemispheric asymmetry in global sea ice changes. *Science*, 278, 1104-1106.
- Dokken, S. T., Haakansson B., and Askne, J. (2000). Inter-Comparison of Arctic Sea Ice Concentration Using RADARSAT, ERS, SSM/I and In-Situ Data, Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing, Vol. 26, No. 6, pp. 521-536.
- Drinkwater, M. R., X. Liu and S. Harms. Combined satellite and ULS-derived sea ice flux in the Weddell Sea. Paper presented at IGS Symposium on Sea Ice and Its Interactions with the Ocean, Atmosphere and Biosphere, June 19 – 23, 2000, Fairbanks.
- Haarpaintner, J., The Storfjorden polynya: ERS-2 SAR observations and overview. *Polar Record* 18(2), 195 – 182, 1999.

- Holt, B., D. A. Rothrock and R. Kwok. Determination of sea ice motion from satellite images. Chapter 18 in *Microwave Remote Sensing of Sea Ice* (Editor F. Carsey) AGU Geophysical Monograph 68, pp. 343 – 354, 1992.
- Johannessen, O. M., W. J. Campbell, R. Shuchman, S. Sandven, P. Gloersen, J. A. Johannessen, E. G. Josberger and P. M. Haugan. Microwave study programs of air-ice-ocean interactive processes in the seasonal ice zone of the Greenland and Barents seas. Chapter 13 in *Microwave Remote Sensing of Sea Ice* (Editor F. Carsey) AGU Geophysical Monograph 68, pp. 261 - 289, 1992.
- Johannessen, O.M., M. Miles and E. Bjørgo, 1995. The Arctic's shrinking sea ice. *Nature*, 376, 126-127.
- Johannessen, O. M., E.V. Shalina and M.W. Miles. Satellite Evidence for an Arctic Sea Ice cover in Transformation. *Science*, 286, 1937-1939. 1999.
- Kreyscher, M., Harder, M., Lemke, P., and Flato, G. M. (2000). Results of the sea ice model intercomparison project: Evaluation of sea ice rheology schemes for use in climate simulations. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 105 (C5), 11299-11320.
- Kwok, R., J. C. Curlander, R. McConnell and S. Pang. An ice motion tracking system at the Alaska SAR facility. *IEEE J. Ocean Engineering*, 15(1), 44 – 54, 1990.
- Kwok, R., G. F. Cunningham, N. LaBele-Hamer, B. Holt and D. Rothrock. Ice thickness derived from high-resolution radar imagery. *EOS Trans. Amer. Geophys. U.*, 80(42), 495, 1999.
- Laxon, S.W. and D. McAdoo, 1994. Arctic Ocean Gravity Field Derived From ERS-1 Satellite Altimetry, *Science*, 265, 621-624.
- Lepparanta, Matti (ed.): "Physics of Ice-Covered Seas." Lectures from Summer school 1994. Helsinki University Printing House 1998, ISBN 951-45-8226-8.
- Loschilov, V.S. and A.: Paramonov: "Determining and mapping the sea ice thickness in the arctic from IR-band satellite imagery". *Earth. Obs. Rem. Sens.*, 1999, Vol.15, pp.763 –775.
- Martin, T. and E. Augstein, Large-scale drift of Arctic Sea ice retrieved from passive microwave satellite data. *J. Geophys. Res. Vol. 105*, No. C4, pp. 8775 – 8788, 2000.
- Onstott, R. G. SAR and Scatterometer signatures of sea ice. Chapter 5 in *Microwave Remote Sensing of Sea Ice* (Editor F. Carsey) AGU Geophysical Monograph 68, pp. 73 - 104, 1992.
- Sandven, S, O. M. Johannessen, Martin Miles, Lasse H. Petterson and K. Kloster. Barents Sea seasonal ice zone features and processes from ERS-1 SAR. *J. Geophys. Res. Vol. 104*, No. C7, p. 15843 – 15857, July 15, 1999.
- Sandven, S., Ø. Dalen, M. Lundhaug, K. Kloster, V.Y. Alexandrov, and L. V. Zaitsev, Sea ice investigations in the Laptev Sea area in late summer using SAR data. *Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 27, no. 5, 502 – 516, 2001.

- Sandven, S., M. Lundhaug, Ø. Dalen, K. Kloster, T. Hamre and V. Alexandrov. SAR study of the transition zone between fastice and drifting ice in the Bothnian Bay in March 1997. Proceedings of The 15th International Conference on Port and Ocean Engineering under Arctic Conditions, Helsinki, Finland, August 23 – 27, 1999a, pp. 518 - 528.
- Sandven, S., M. Lundhaug, Ø. Dalen, K. Kloster and V. Alexandrov. Satellite observations of sea ice in the Bothnian Bay. In *Local Ice Cover Deformation and mesoscale Ice Dynamics* (Ed. Riska and Tuhkuri), *Part 1: Final Scientific Report* from the “Ice State” project funded by EU MAST III. Helsinki University of Technology, Ship Laboratory, M-242, 393 pp, Espoo 1999b.
- Shuchman, R. A. and R. G. Onstott. Remote sensing of Polar Oceans. In *Polar Oceanography, Part A: Physical Science* (Edited by W. O. Smith jr.) pp. 123 - 169, 1990.
- Smith, D. M., 1998. Recent increase in the length of the melt season of perennial Arctic sea ice. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 25, 655-658.
- Steffen, K., J. Key, D.J. Cavalieri, J. Comiso, P. Gloersen, K. St. Germain and I. Rubinstein, 1992. The estimation of geophysical parameters using passive microwave algorithms. In F. Carsey (ed.) *Microwave Remote Sensing of Sea Ice* AGU Geophysical Monograph 68, pp. 201-231.
- Svendsen, E., K. Kloster, B. Farrelly, O. M. Johannessen, J. A. Johannessen, W. J. Campbell, P. Gloersen, D. J. Cavalieri and C. Maetzler. Norwegian Remote Sensing Experiment: Evaluation of the Nimbus 7 Scanning Multichannel microwave Radiometer for sea ice research. *J. Geophys. Res.* 88 (C5), pp. 2781 – 2792, 1983.
- Vinje, T., N. Nordlund and Å. Kvambekk, Monitoring ice thickness in Fram Strait, *J. Geophys. Res.* 103, C5, 10437 – 10449, 1998
- Wackerman, C. C, D. Miller. An automated algorithm for sea ice classification in the Marginal Ice Zone using ERS-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar. ERIM Technical Report, 1996.
- Wadhams, P. *Ice in the Ocean*. Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, The Netherlands, 2000, 351 pp.
- WMO Sea Ice Nomenclature, WMO report no. 259, TP 145, 1970/1985.

Appendix A: Sea ice_glossary

- Belt:** A large feature of pack ice, longer than it is wide, from 1 km to more than 100 km in width.
- Bergy bit:** A large piece of floating glacier ice, generally showing less than 5 m and more than 1 m above sea level, nominally about 100-300 m² in area.
- Bight:** An extensive crescent-shaped indentation in the ice edge, formed by either wind or current.
- Brash ice:** Accumulation of floating ice made up of fragments not more than 2 m across (small ice cakes), the wreckage of other forms of ice.
- Break up:** A general expression applied to the formation of a large number of fractures through a compact ice cover, followed by a rapid diverging motion of the separate fragments.
- Compact ice edge:** Close, clear-cut ice edge compacted by wind or current; usually on the windward side of pack ice.
- Compactness:** The ration of the area of the sea surface actually %covered by ice to the total area of the sea surface under consideration, %Therefore, a compactness of 0 corresponds to ice free and a compactness % of 1 to compact ice.
- Concentration:** The ratio of the sea surface area covered by ice of any type to the total sea surface area within a defined area. May be expressed in the following terms:
Compact ice: Concentration 10/10, no water visible
Consolidated ice: Concentration 10/10, floes frozen together
Very close ice: Concentration 9/10 to less than 10/10
Close ice: Concentration 7/10 to 8/10, floes mostly in contact
Open ice: Concentration 4/10 to 6/10, many leads and polynyas, floes generally not in contact.
Very open ice: Concentration 1/10 to 3/10.
- Consolidated pack ice:** Pack ice in which the concentration is 10/10 (8/8) and the floes are frozen together.
- Crack:** Any fracture which has not yet parted.
- Deformed ice:** A general term for ice which has been squeezed together and in places forced upward (and downward). Forms of deformation include rafting, ridging and hummocking.
- Diffuse ice edge:** Poorly defined ice edge limiting an area of dispersed ice ; usually on the leeward side of an area of pack ice.
- Diverging ice:** Used to indicate a general diverging motion, reducing concentration or relieving stress.
- Draft:** The distance, measured normal to the sea surface, between the lower surface of the ice and the water level.
- Fast ice:** Sea ice of any origin which remains fast (attached with little horizontal motion) along a coast or to some other fixed object.
- Fast ice boundary:** The ice boundary at any given time between fast ice and pack ice.
- Fast ice edge:** The demarcation at any given time between fast ice and open water.
- Firstyear ice:** Sea ice of not more than one winter's growth, developing from young ice. Thickness 0.3-3 m. May be subdivided into thin firstyear ice/white ice (0.3-0.7 m), medium firstyear ice (0.7-1.2 m) and thick firstyear ice (over 1.2 m).

Flaw: A narrow separation zone between pack ice and fast ice, where the pieces of ice are in a chaotic state, that forms when pack ice shears under the effect of a strong wind or current along the fast ice boundary.

Flaw lead: A passage between pack ice and fast ice, navigable by a vessel.

Floe: Any relatively flat piece of sea ice 20 m or more across. Floes are subdivided according to horizontal extent

Giant floe: more than 10 km across

Vast floe: 2--10 km across

Big floe: 0.5--2 km across

Medium floe: 100--500 m across

Small floe: 20--100 m across.

Flooded ice: Sea ice which has been flooded by melt-water or river water and is heavily loaded by water and wet snow.

Fracture: Any break or rupture through very close, compact or consolidate pack ice, fast ice or a single floe resulting from deformation processes (cf. lead). Fractures may contain brash ice and be covered with nilas or young ice. The length may be a few meters or many kilometers.

Frazil ice: Fine spicules or plates of ice, suspended in water.

Freeboard: The distance, measured normal to the surface, between the upper surface of the ice and the water level.

Grease ice: A stage of freezing, in which the crystals have coagulated to form a soupy layer on the surface which reflects little backscatter.

Grey ice: Young ice, 10--15 cm thick, less elastic than nilas, usually rafts under pressure.

Grey-white ice: Young ice, 15--30 cm thick. Under pressure, it is more likely to ridge than to raft.

Grounded ice: Floating ice (e.g. ridge, hummock and ice island) which is aground (stranded) in shoal water.

Hummock: A pile of broken ice which has been forced upward by pressure. May be fresh or weathered. The submerged volume of broken ice under the hummock is called a bummock.

Iceberg: A massive piece of ice of greatly varying shape with a freeboard of more than 5 m, which has broken away from a glacier and may be afloat or aground.

Ice boundary: The demarcation at any given time between fast ice and pack ice or between areas of pack ice of different concentrations (cf. ice edge).

Ice breccia: Ice pieces of different age frozen together.

Ice cake: Any relatively flat piece of sea ice less than 20 m across (cf. floe). If less than 2 m across, it is a small ice cake.

Ice cover: The ratio of an area of ice of any concentration to the total area of sea surface within some large geographic area; this area may be global, hemispheric, or prescribed by a specific oceanographic entity, such as Baffin Bay or the Barents Sea.

Ice edge: The demarcation at any given time between the open sea and sea ice of any kind. It may be compact or diffuse.

Ice field: Area of pack ice greater than 10 km across (cf. ice patch), consisting of floes of any size.

Subdivided as follows:

Large ice field: more than 20 km across

Medium ice field: 15--20 km across

Small ice field: 10--15 km across

Ice free: No sea ice present. There may, however, be some icebergs present (see also open water).

Ice island: A large piece of floating ice about 5 m above sea level, which has broken away from an Arctic ice shelf, having a thickness of 30-50 m and an area of from a few thousand square meters to more than 100 km² and usually characterized by a regularly undulating surface which gives it a ribbed appearance from the air.

Ice jam: An accumulation of broken river ice or sea ice caught in a narrow channel.

Ice limit: Climatological term referring to the extreme minimum or extreme maximum extent of the ice edge in any given month or period, based on observations over a number of years.

Ice massif: A concentration of sea ice covering hundreds of nautical miles square, which is found in the same region every summer.

Ice patch: An area of pack ice less than 5.4 n. mile across.

Ice shelf: A floating ice sheet of considerable thickness, showing 2--50 m or more above sea level, attached to the coast. Usually of great horizontal extent and with a level or gently undulating surface. The ice sheet is caused by glaciers extending into the ocean, so parts of it may be aground. The seaward edge is called an ice front.

Keel: The underside of a ridge that projects downward below the lower surface of the surrounding sea ice.

Lead: Any fracture or passage through sea ice that is generally navigable by a vessel. A lead may contain open water (open lead) or be covered by thin ice (frozen lead).

Level ice: Sea ice which has been unaffected by deformation.

Melt pond: An accumulation of meltwater on the surface of sea ice.

Multiyear ice: Old ice 3 m or more thick, which has survived at least two summers' melt. The hummocks are even smoother than in secondyear ice, and the ice is almost salt-free. The color, where bare, is usually blue. The melt pattern consists of large inter-connecting irregular puddles and melt ponds, and a well-developed drainage system. In remote sensing, note that secondyear ice is often referred to as multiyear ice.

New ice: A general term for recently formed ice, which includes frazil ice, grease ice, slush and shuga. These types of ice are composed of ice crystals which are only weakly frozen together (if at all) and have a definite form only while they are afloat.

Nilas: A thin elastic crust of ice up to 10 cm thick. Bends easily under pressure, thrusting in a pattern of interlocking "fingers" (finger rafting). Dark nilas, up to 5 cm thick is very dark in color; light nilas, 5--10 cm thick, is rather lighter in color.

Old ice: Sea ice which has survived at least one summers melt. Most topographic features are smoother than firstyear ice. May be subdivided into secondyear ice and multiyear ice.

Open water: A large area of freely navigable water in which sea ice is present in less than 1/10 concentration (see also ice free).

- Pack ice: Any accumulation of sea ice, other than fast ice, no matter what form it takes or how it is disposed.
- Pancake ice: Predominantly circular pieces of ice from 0.3--3 m in diameter, and up to about 10 cm in thickness, with raised rims due to the pieces striking against one another. It may be formed on a slight swell from grease ice, shuga or slush, or as a result of the breaking up of ice rind, nilas, or under severe conditions of swell or waves, grey ice. It also sometimes forms at some depth, at an interface between water bodies of different physical characteristics, and floats to the surface. It may rapidly cover wide areas of water.
- Polynyas: Any nonlinear shaped opening enclosed in ice. Polynyas may contain brash ice or be covered with new ice, nilas or young ice. If it is limited on one side by the coast, it is called shore polynya; if limited by fast ice, it is called a flaw polynya and if found in the same place every year, it is called a recurring polynya.
- Pressure ridge: A general expression for any elongated (in plain view) ridgelike accumulation of broken ice forced up by converging ice (ridging).
- Rafting: Process whereby one piece of ice overrides another. Most obvious in new and young ice but common in ice of all thickness.
- Residual firstyear ice: Russian term for old ice.
- Ridging: See pressure ridge.
- River ice: Ice formed on a river, regardless of observed location.
- Rubble Field: An area of sea ice that has essentially all beendeformed. Also called hummock field.
- Secondyear ice: Ice which has survived only one summers' melt. In contrast to multiyear ice, secondyear ice during the summer melt shows a regular pattern of numerous small puddles.
- Shear zone: An area in which a large amount of shearing deformation has been concentrated.
- Shore lead: A lead between pack ice and the shore or between pack ice and an ice shelf or a glacier.
- Shuga: An accumulation of spongy white ice lumps a few centimeters across, formed from grease ice or slush and sometimes from anchor ice rising to the surface.
- Slush: Snow which is saturated and mixed with water on land or ice surfaces, or forms as a viscous mass floating in water after a heavy snowfall.
- Snow ice: The equigranular ice that is produced when slush freezes completely.
- Stranded ice: Ice which has been floating and has been deposited on the shore by retreating high water.
- Tabular iceberg: A flat-topped iceberg. Most tabular icebergs form by calving from an ice shelf and show horizontal banding (see also ice island).
- White ice: See thin firstyear ice.
- Young ice: Ice in the transition stage between nilas and firstyear ice, 10--30 cm thick. May be subdivided into grey ice and grey-white ice. The expression young ice is also commonly used in a more general way to indicate the complete range of ice thickness between 0 and 30 cm. Usually these difference in meaning are clear from the context of the discussion.